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NODES
Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

SPACE4YOU LAB DESCRIPTION

SPOKE1

SPace Activities and CompEtences for industrY bOost in bUsiness

DELIVERABLE D1

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

Space4You Lab description

SPace Activities and CompEtences for industrY bOost in bUusiness

Space4You

SPOKE N 1 Deliverable 1

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The proposed laboratory, Space4You, shall tackle the challenges stemming out from the great attention devoted by the industry to Space and the consequential opportunities. The initial set-up of the lab addressed several different aspects related to the consolidation of the research work of the different teams and the coordination in a unified framework able to provide solutions for increasing the capabilities and outcomes of small satellites missions.

In particular the work is developed in the areas of:

- Design of space architectures for supporting innovative applications and services
- Development of technologies, materials, equipment, and processes for preparation and sustainable implementation of new applications
- Solutions for increasing autonomy of space habitats

As part of the Research Booster methodology of NODES, Space4You will carry out applied research activities with and for companies, to ensure an effective interaction between leading universities and research centers, scientific and industrial associations, important players from the industry, society, and policy makers. It will nurture ideas, inventions, and innovations generated in universities and will transfer them to the industrial and social networks, fostering the relations, synergies, and cross-fertilization between different sectors.

1.2 Implementation

During these first months of the project the initial work was devoted to organize and set-up in a unified framework different contribution by the research partners, which, by themselves, are already performing high-level investigations in the field of applied research for Space.

The management of the project is fostering the development of joint activities between the different participants in order to create a coordinated critical mass of competences, founded on solid interdisciplinary scientific research.

The creation of common physical shared spaces for the lab would be a meaningful milestone of Space4You, also in light of the establishment of the Città dell'Aerospazio in the Turin area, as a common interface for the industry. The limitations of the NODES project in terms of timeframe and budget do not allow a full implementation to be reached. However, the NODES activities, and the collaboration within the partners will allow to develop a shared implementation plan involving the different partners, but also obtaining the requirements and the needs through the stakeholder committee and feedbacks by the industry partners.

A tangible outcome of Space4You is the creation of a Space4You knowledge portal, i.e., an accessible database of the competences and skills available in the research aerospace ecosystem, as described in Section 5.

2 Participants

2.1 Politecnico di Torino

The activities of the Spoke 1 pertaining to the aerospace field will benefit from the strong research legacy of Polito in these areas and the presence of consolidated partnerships with leading industrial players. Politecnico has established interdepartmental centers in order to enhance interdisciplinary collaborations and improve the transformation of research results into innovation. The departments and the centers cover an extensive range of relevant technologies, research infrastructures and skills for supporting innovation and technology transfer in the aerospace domain. PoliTo is currently participating in several EU funded projects related to Aerospace topics. PoliTo is heavily involved in contracts with the European Space Agency on a wide variety of subjects for upstream and downstream development. On the same topics, PoliTo has different collaborations with the main international research centers and universities, as well as with the local stakeholders of the aerospace supply chain. PoliTO has several departmental labs devoted to space-related activities (some shared with LINKS Foundation), including nanosatellites development and full lifecycle assessment. Many research groups are involved in projects in the aerospace domain in collaboration with most notable public institutions and private companies in the field, such as NASA/JPL, NASA/Goddard, the European and Italian Space Agencies, DLR, Leonardo, Thales Alenia Space, Avio, Altec, Sitael, OHB and Airbus. Partnership agreements are in place between PoliTo and ASI, Leonardo and Thales. PoliTo is contributing to the **large-scale project Turin Aerospace City that pursues the creation of an international cluster in aerospace. The Turin Aerospace City is based on the contribution of academic labs, leading aerospace multinationals, SMEs and start-ups according to an innovation ecosystem approach** thanks to a strong commitment of the Piemonte Regional government.

The Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (DIMEAS) will contribute to Space4You with the expertise of different research groups. They offer expertise on upstream and downstream applications. In the upstream domain: mission and systems design (using Concurrent Engineering and Model-Based Systems Engineering approaches), systems and subsystems modelling (orbit propagators, CubeSat dynamics, GNC/AOCS sensors and actuators models, as well as visual navigation algorithms, thermo-mechanical systems modelling (using embedded control sensing/monitoring applied to the energy supply units for manned exploration operations support), manufacturing processes and solutions such as application of plasma treatments for the production of sustainable structural composites. In the downstream domain: use of earth observation satellites and gap-filling artificial intelligence algorithms for ocean monitoring and offshore renewable energy.

The Department of Electronics and Telecommunications (DET) will contribute to Space4You with the specific studies and facilities development in the field of telecommunications and navigation/positioning. The team involved have a strong background in the field, and an excellent publication record, as well as a consolidated experience in research projects with the industries.

The Department of Control and Computer Engineering (DAUIN) will contribute to Space4You with the activities focused on computing tools and design methodologies applicable to the early development stage of a space satellites up to the realization of high performance and resilient computing platform for increased on-board processing capabilities.

The Department of Industrial Engineering and Management (DIGEP) will contribute to Space4You with the identification of the technological trajectories and new entrepreneurial ventures in the space domain, discussing the role of innovation ecosystems. The research lines addressed by DIGEP aims at improving our understanding of the key factors that affect the process of new business creation and growth in the field of aerospace. Such factors pertain both to new business opportunities engendered by technological change and to the localized interaction dynamics among different players of the innovation ecosystem.

The Department of Applied Science and Technology (DISAT) will contribute to Space4You with its expertise in 3D printing (Digital Light Processing, DLP; Direct Ink Writing, DIW) of engineering ceramics, materials synthesis, processing and characterization, ceramics for high temperatures and harsh environments, CO2 capturing materials, joining and coating of materials and their testing in relevant conditions, joining materials and processing design and optimization.

The Department of Structural, Geotechnical and Building Engineering (DISEG) will contribute to Space4You with the expertise in the design and realization of optimized structures models for space infrastructures, with a focus on Creation of self-assembling and self-supporting smart structures.

The Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) contributes to Space4You with its expertise in 3D models using remotely sensed data at different geometric and spectral resolution.

2.2 University of Torino

The University of Turin (UniTo) participates to the Space4You project with the Departments of Chemistry, Physics, and Mathematics. In addition, UniTO, shares in the Space4You project its own innovation ecosystem represented by the interdepartment centers NIS (on Nanomaterials <https://www.nis.unito.it>) and ICxT (on Digital and Circular Technologies for Society, <https://icxt.di.unito.it/>) and the associated network of scientific collaborations with companies and research centers.

The Department of Chemistry will contribute to Space4You with activities in the field of materials science applied to space exploration and space services. In particular, the activity will be focused on the development of organic materials for light weight and foldable photovoltaic arrays. In addition, the Department will contribute to the ecosystem with expertise in the fields of thermal and radiation shields, chemistry of Life support Systems and In Situ Resources Utilization.

The Department of Physics will contribute to Space4You with its lab devoted to the development of satellite-based X-ray sensors for space and earth observation, and advanced data analysis of observational data.

The Department of Mathematics will contribute to Space4You with competences in the field of the simulation of aggregation and movement of celestial bodies and other structures, optimization, stability and control of trajectories in space.

2.3 LINKS foundation

The LINKS Foundation – Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society- is a non-profit private Foundation founded in 2018 to boost the interaction between research and the business world towards the internationalization of the local socio-economic system. LINKS promotes, conducts, and strengthens innovation and research project processes, improving product implementation and the study of new approaches and models. LINKS is the result of merging two distinguished research and innovation institutions: ISMB (Istituto Superiore Mario Boella), focusing on ICT, and SiTI (Istituto Superiore sui Sistemi Territoriali per l'Innovazione), focusing on Territorial Systems and Smart Cities. Similarly, to ISMB and SITI, LINKS has been founded by Compagnia di San Paolo and Politecnico di Torino, inheriting the existing background of ISMB and SiTI in terms of personnel knowledge, facilities, goods, and premises.

LINKS relies on the technological competencies of around 160 researchers and works in close cooperation with companies, academia, and Public Administration and oversees technical-scientific disciplines in digital technology and regional development such as Artificial Intelligence, connected systems, and IoT, cybersecurity, advanced calculation systems, satellite systems. All this is then applied to innovative projects in many application fields such as industry 4.0, Intelligent Mobility, Agritech, Space Economy, Smart infrastructures, and Cultural Heritage.

Two research domains of LINKS Foundation will be involved in the Space4You flagship project: AI, Data and Space (ADS), and Advanced Computing, Photonics and Electromagnetics (CPE).

ADS focuses on the realization of intelligent digital applications capable of addressing the key challenges associated with industrial and societal needs coupling both the use of Artificial Intelligence and Data, often received from satellites systems. The department counts on vertical skills on Artificial Intelligence, data science and engineering, and space technologies. Researchers master the entire data value chain, developing systems for data generation and collection from a variety of sources including space, data processing through advanced algorithms and techniques, and for delivering visual outputs through effective and usable human to machine interfaces. Researchers implement machine learning and knowledge graphs in the field of Artificial intelligence for creating intelligent applications able to work symbiotically with human beings in defined tasks. Artificial Intelligence applications include advanced web search engines, recommendation systems, language understanding, vision, self-driving cars, and competing at the highest level in strategic game systems.

CPE has developed over the years a great expertise in cloud and high-performance computing (HPC) with several collaboration with industry (e.g. ST Microelectronics, AVIO Aero, etc.) as well as the participation to European Projects, like ACROSS focused on the development of a platform able to combine traditional HPC techniques with Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Big Data analytic techniques.

3 Research Teams

In the following sections, a short description of the expertise of the different research groups is provided. The research groups belong to different departments and areas of Polito, Unito and Links, and in case of large departments, there are different groups with different expertise within the same department.

3.1 POLITO-DISAT (LINCE)

3.1.1 Group description

LINCE Center (Laboratorio di Tecnologia e Ingegnerizzazione dei Materiali Ceramici) comprises three INSTM research units (Politecnico di Torino, Università degli Studi di Cagliari and Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia) with the primary goal of establishing a prominent presence in ceramic materials technology and engineering.

The center operates on two distinct levels. On one hand, LINCE boasts expertise in both basic and applied research, actively involved in conceiving new materials for structural and functional applications, thus fostering scientific innovation in this field. On the other hand, the members of the group have extensive experience in collaborating with the industrial production sector.

In particular, **LINCE Team at Politecnico di Torino** leads in the design and development of engineered oxide ceramics.

Expertise@Lince includes:

- Synthesis of monophasic ceramics and ceramic nanocomposites with superior properties for application in harsh environmental conditions
- Tailored porous and functionally graded ceramics
- Additive manufacturing
- Self-sensing and self-healing ceramic materials
- Carbon capture materials
- Development of ceramic suspensions for Thermal barrier coatings

Alongside conducting advanced research, LINCE team also offers support to companies in areas such as characterization, quality control, and problem-solving across diverse application fields.

As a result, over years the LINCE team has established numerous collaborations with both university research center and companies in Italy and Europe providing a valuable contribution in technical ceramic research advancement.

Projects:

- **AMITIE PROJECT** (Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant Agreement 734342, <http://www.rise-amicie.eu/>) in which eleven academic and nine industrial partners from eight different countries are involved. The goal of the AMITIE project was to **promote research and innovation in additive manufacturing of ceramics through international and intersectoral staff exchange**. Several big worldwide companies were involved such as Saint-Gobain, Bosch, Kyocera, Swatch Group etc.
- **CONCERTO PROJECT** (<https://www.concerto-prin.it/>) Multiscale modelling/characterisation and fabrication of nanocomposite ceramics with improved toughness. Aim of the project is **to support and accelerate the production of Ce-TZP nanocomposites and coatings, with unprecedented combination between strength and toughness**. The consortium is composed of five academic partners and two impactful case studies are selected to demonstrate the relevance of the research conducted, namely optimization and functional validation of (a) Ce-TZP materials for application in dental prostheses and (b) Ce-TZP composite thermal barrier coatings for high-temperature applications.

Publications:

1. Bartolomeo Coppola, Julien Schmitt, Tanguy Lacondemine, Caroline Tardivat, Laura Montanaro, Paola Palmero, Digital light processing stereolithography of zirconia ceramics: Slurry elaboration and orientation-reliant mechanical properties, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, Volume 42, Issue 6, 2022, Pages 2974-2982, ISSN 0955-2219, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.01.024>.
2. Bartolomeo Coppola, Tanguy Lacondemine, Caroline Tardivat, Laura Montanaro, Paola Palmero, Designing alumina-zirconia composites by DLP-based stereolithography: Microstructural tailoring and mechanical performances, *Ceramics International*, Volume 47, Issue 10, Part A, 2021, Pages 13457-13468, ISSN 0272-8842, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.01.204>.
3. Barbara Inserra, Bartolomeo Coppola, Laura Montanaro, Jean-Marc Tulliani, Paola Palmero, Preparation and characterization of Ce-ZrO₂/Al₂O₃ composites by DLP-based stereolithography, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, Volume 43, Issue 7, 2023, Pages 2907-2916, ISSN 0955-2219, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.08.037>.

3.1.2 Facilities

The LINCE laboratories at Politecnico di Torino are equipped with advanced technologies for the synthesis, characterization and shaping of technical ceramics and composite materials.

- Spray dryer
- Rotary evaporator
- Laser granulometry-particle size analyzer
- Thermal analyses: Thermogravimetric/differential thermal analysis (ATG-DTA) up to 1600 °C and dilatometer
- Rheometer for viscosity assessment
- Additive manufacturing equipment for ceramic shaping: Digital Light Processing (DLP) and Robocasting
- High temperature furnaces for ceramic sintering
- Tensile and bending test for mechanical properties assessment
- Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM)
- X-ray diffractometer (XRD)
- X-ray fluorescence (XRF) for the analysis of elemental composition and chemical and electronic state of the atoms within a material

- Temperature-controlled laboratory facility for testing gas and humidity sensors
- Climatic chambers
- Mercury porosimeter for determining pore size from 6 nm to 400 microns

3.1.3 Outcomes from Space4You

Lince team will contribute to Space4You by the development of new materials and processes for new space applications. In fact, different classes of advanced ceramics find application in this field due to their exceptional dimensional/chemical stability over a wide temperature range and high corrosion resistance, as well as a lower density compared to metal-based components, thus allowing faster speeds to be achieved while ensuring low fuel consumption. Furthermore, advanced ceramics can be used for the manufacturing of piezoelectric, thermoelectric and electrochemical sensing devices, showing a great potential in the space industry.

In particular, the research activity will focus on:

- Synthesis and characterization of novel advanced ceramics and ceramic nanocomposite materials with tailored microstructural/mechanical properties for high temperature and extreme environmental applications.
- 3D printing technologies for advanced ceramic processing, including Digital Light Processing (DLP) and Direct Ink Writing (DIW) for producing new generation aerospace components with superior surface finishing and spatial resolution suitable for operating in harsh environments.
- Functional ceramic systems based on CO₂ capturing materials to preserve space habitat, and limit pollutions.

3.1.4 Foreseen research collaborations

LINCE Team possesses innovative facilities and cross-disciplinary expertise that foster collaboration with other research groups within Space4You. In particular, LINCE Team will collaborate with the other research units in terms of materials engineering, characterization and optimization. Indeed, LINCE Team can provide specific and advanced competences in the field of advanced ceramics and materials for harsh environments. Finally, LINCE Team has a well-established know-how in ceramics additive manufacturing, with particular attention to direct ink writing (DIW) and digital light processing (DIW). Thus, LINCE Team can develop formulations, 3D printed prototypes and samples that can be characterized in terms of physical, mechanical and microstructural properties.

3.2 POLITO-DISAT (Glance)

3.2.1 Group description

Glance (Glass, Ceramics and Composites team) group of DISAT has a huge expertise in joining/coating of CMC and ceramics (<http://www.composites.polito.it>) for several applications (aerospace, high -temperature applications, harsh environment, automotive, etc) . Over the past three decades, Glance has made significant advancements in pressure-less joining materials, specifically in joining ceramic-based materials to themselves and dissimilar materials. The research group involved in the project is a leading authority in ceramic joining and coating, boasting an impressive portfolio of more than 10 patents and coordination and participation in 20+ EU projects in this field.

The research facilities at DISAT (Department of Applied Science and Technology) are well-equipped to support the production, characterization, and mechanical testing of composites, nanocomposites, fibres, and surface modification. These facilities, detailed at <http://www.composites.polito.it/>, offer comprehensive resources that can be utilized for the project. Moreover, the research group is an integral part of J-TECH@POLITO, an advanced joining technologies research centre at POLITO. This inter-departmental, multi-disciplinary centre involves three departments and 25+ staff members, providing additional specialized facilities for joining and testing (<http://www.j-tech.polito.it/facilities>).

Selection of EU projects and patents relevant to Space4You:

- **CEM-WAVE**: Novel Ceramic Matrix Composites produced with Microwave assisted Chemical Vapour Infiltration process for energy-intensive industries. LC-SPIRE-08-2020 - Novel high performance materials and components (RIA) GE n. 958170. 1/10/2020-31/3/2024.
- **CoACH**: Advanced glasses, Composites And Ceramics for High growth Industries - European Training Network. H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014 GA 642557. 1/1/2015-31/12/2018.
- **GLACERCo**: “Glasses and Ceramic Composites for High Technology Applications. FP7-PEOPLE-2010-ITN GA 264526. 01/02/2011- 31/1/2015
- **ADMACOM**: Advanced manufacturing routes for metal/Composite components for Aerospace FP7. FoF.NMP.2013 GA 609188. 1/10/2013-30/09/2016.
- **JOLIE**: JOining of LIghtweight alloys to advanced FGM mEtal-ceramic materials. MATERA ERANET n. 2227. 1/7/2012-30/6/2015.
- **KMM-NoE Network of Excellence**: Knowledge based Multicomponent Materials for Durable and Safe Performance. FP6- Network of excellence FP6-NMP 502243. 1/11/2004-31/10/2008.
- **NEXTOWER**: Advanced materials solutions for next generation high efficiency concentrated solar power (CSP) tower systems. H2020 - NMBP-17-2016. 01/01/2017-31/12/2020.
- **Enabling Research Project, EUROFUSION** - Optimization and characterization of tungsten steel joints for the plasma facing wall using different coating technologies including FGM techniques”. EURATOM: Enabling Research Program (CfP-WP14-ER-01/FZJ-10). 01/01/2017- 31/12/2018.
- **CASTLE**: Cabin Systems design Toward passenger wellBeing. PROGRAMMA CLEAN SKY 2 - CALL ID: H2020-CS2-CPW02-2015-01 - TOPIC-AIR-02-08. 01/07/2016 - 31/03/2022.
- **IL TROVATORE**: Innovative cladding materials for advanced accident-tolerant energy systems. EURATOM. H2020- NFRP-2016-2017-01- GA N°740415. 01/10/2017-31/03/2022.
- **INN VIN (FP7)**: Innovative materials solutions for Transport, Energy and Biomedical sectors by strengthening integration and enhancing research dynamics of KMM-VIN. FP7 – EU - Coordination and support action, GA: 290526. 1/2/2012- 31/1/2015.
- **ExtreMat**: - New materials for extreme environments. FP6 project no. NMP3-CT-2004-500253. 1/12/2004-31/10/2010.
- **MATRANS**: Micro and Nanocrystalline Functionally Graded Materials for Transport Applications. FP7 project -NMP -2008-SMALL-2 project no. GA 228869. 1/2/2010-31/1/2013.
- **ESA LET-SME ACTIVITIES**- Carbon Based Adhesive, funded by European Space Agency. n° 20479/06/NL/Sfe.22/03/2010-31/05/2011.

Patent n. EP2214732., Process to join carbon based materials to metals and its applications, Owner: POLITECNICO DI TORINO Authors: FERRARIS M., CASALEGNO V., SALVO M., 2005, Publication info: EP1685079 (A1) — 2006-08-02. International Publication number WO 2005/037734 A1

3.2.2 Facilities

GLANCE and J-Tech@POLITO laboratories are fully equipped for the research and development of glasses, glass-ceramics, ceramics and composites.

Facilities include: Micro-CT, high T mechanical test equipment, profilometer, UV-Vis, Vis-NIR, EDS, XPS, Sputtering (DC, Pulsed DC, RF magnetron sputtering), laser welding, laser and plasma surface treatment, Electrophoretic Deposition, Heating microscope, high-T furnaces, cutting and polishing machines, thermal analysis (DSC, DTA up to 1500°C, DMA, dilatometer up to 1550°C), SEM, FESEM, STEM, AFM, hot stage X-ray diffraction and SAXS, μ -XRD, environmental chambers and electrokinetic measurements of zeta potential of bulk samples (SurPASS).

These facilities are detailed (max working T, atmosphere, size, etc) at <http://www.composites.polito.it/> and at <http://www.j-tech.polito.it/facilities/>.

3.2.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The research activity carried out in Space4You will define a methodology for the surface structuring of composites (both polymeric and ceramic). Surface modification technologies are considered along with new joining methods and materials for composites for improving the characteristics of joined components.

The relevance of ceramic based composites or CFRP as emerging advanced materials can be still more strengthened developing easier and more rapid techniques for the joining among composites or with dissimilar materials (i.e metals), which would open the use of these materials to several strategic applications. DISAT unit will study the feasibility of the texturing of ceramic surfaces and CFRP by Atmospheric-pressure plasmas (APPs).

Texturing-induced mechanical anchoring is anticipated to significantly bolster the mechanical strength of bonded samples, resulting in cohesive failure. The incorporation of surface modification techniques, in conjunction with appropriate joining materials, can greatly enhance the overall value of the proposed undertaking. Once the parameters for generating a textured composite surface are defined, the surfaces of the specimens will be meticulously assessed to evaluate their topography. Subsequently, bending tests will be conducted to quantify the impact of the modification process on both treated and non-treated samples.

3.2.4 Foreseen research collaborations

A mutual activity with POLITO/DIMEAS unit will be carried on, focusing on the investigation of surface modification processes on polymeric-based composites reinforced by C fibers. DISAT unit will supply the microstructural characterization of the modified surfaces by means of microscopic analysis by OM and SEM coupled with EDS, zeta potential and micro-CT, accordingly to what detailed in the previous paragraph.

3.3 POLITO-DIMEAS (MAM-MT)

3.3.1 Group description

Mechanics of Advanced Materials - Modelling and Testing (MAM-MT) systematically investigates issues relevant to the production, mechanical properties, numerical simulations and applications of composite and lightweight materials. Specifically, MAM-MT does research on experimental tests, analytical and numerical modelling of these materials. The scope of MAM-MT is to study and explore the mechanical response of new lightweight advanced materials and structures. MAM-MT particularly focuses on the development and use of multifunctional materials, sustainable composite materials, non-destructive analysis for damage detection, structural optimization and advanced testing. The main investigated topics are:

- Replacement of structural composites with new bio-based resin and natural fibres;
- Structural health monitoring and healing of composite materials;
- Design and optimization of composite components for crash absorption events;
- Non-destructive analysis for damage detection in composite components;
- Static and dynamic properties of composite materials for numerical simulations;
- Replacement of chemical treatments of fibers with more sustainable plasma treatments;
- Impact behavior of composite materials;
- Low Cycle Fatigue (LCF), High Cycle Fatigue (HCF) and Very High Cycle Fatigue (VHCF) of composite and lightweight metal materials;
- Application of Machine Learning methods for efficient predictions of composite material behavior;
- Multiscale modelling of composite structures;
- Adhesive joining of composite materials.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Boursier Niutta C, Ciardiello R, Tridello A, Paolino DS. Epoxy and Bio-Based Epoxy Carbon Fiber Twill Composites: Comparison of the Quasi-Static Properties. *Materials*. 2023; 16(4):1601. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16041601>
- [2] Ciardiello R, D'Angelo D, Cagna L, Croce A, Paolino DS. Effects of plasma treatments of polypropylene adhesive joints used in the automotive industry. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*. 2022;236(11):6204-6218. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09544062211065361>
- [3] Boursier Niutta C, Tridello A, Paolino DS, Belingardi G. Residual Properties in Damaged Laminated Composites through Nondestructive Testing: A Review. *Materials*. 2021; 14(16):4513. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14164513>
- [4] Ciampaglia A, Fiumarella D, Boursier Niutta C, Ciardiello R, Belingardi G. Impact response of an origami-shaped composite crash box: Experimental analysis and numerical optimization. *Composite Structures* 2021; 256:113093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.11309>

Selected project of the research group relevant to Space4you:

AMICO, Additive manufacturing and process automation for hybrid and composite materials	The AMICO project aimed at using additive manufacturing processes for creating new and advanced composite materials. The MAMMT/POLIVE group has worked on the mechanical characterization of composite materials manufactured with additive processes. In this activity, the Group has used optic fibre sensors and the innovative use of impulse excitation technique to monitor and detect the crack propagation on composite materials.
GF4C - Green Factory for Composites	GF4C project aimed at finding innovative manufacturing solutions for enhancing the eco-production of high-performing composites. Production and use of innovative composite materials for structural and health monitoring applications. The research Group worked on the mechanical and numerical characterisation of composite materials produced with green methodologies made of different fibres and different matrixes (thermosets and thermoplastics).
Fatigue4Light – Fatigue for Lightweight	Fatigue4Light uses advanced numerical simulation tools and experimental techniques to assure part performance and reduce the lead times for the market introduction of new light and high-performance chassis parts. The research group validated an experimental approach for assessing material defectiveness with ultrasonic Very-High-Cycle-Fatigue (VHCF) tests. The group implemented a software code for the prediction of the fatigue strength and life of components.
INNUMAT - Innovative structural materials for nuclear applications	The main objectives of INNUMAT are to develop innovative structural materials for nuclear applications and put them on track towards qualification for fission lead-cooled and molten salt fast reactors as well as fusion DEMO. The research unit will carry out fatigue tests in dynamic conditions and Low Cycle Fatigue range under different temperature conditions. Thus, will be in charge to study the collapsing behaviour and the crack propagation under fatigue loads.
ICONIC-ITN (Improving Crashworthiness of Composite Transportation Structures)	The central aim of ICONIC is to develop a critical mass of gender-balanced research and engineering leaders, across Europe, with a world-leading capability in the design of lightweight aeronautical, automotive and rail transportation composite structures with superior crashworthiness. The research unit worked on the lightweight design and testing of composite material structures used in the automotive industries under crash impacts.

3.3.2 Facilities

X-ray Computed tomography (Fraunhofer IKTS)	Maximum operating voltage: 300 kV. Resolution: about 5 μm . Sample size: max 500 mm x 500 mm x 500 mm (L x W x H). Sample weight: max 100 kg.
Electrodynamic testing machine for combined axial-torsional fatigue tests (Electroforce 3550 - TA Instruments)	Maximum axial load: 15 kN. Maximum torsional moment: 70 Nm. Maximum loading frequency: 50 Hz.
Impulse Excitation Technique Testing equipment (RFDA HT1600 – IMCE)	Non-destructive test based on Impulse Excitation Technique for measurement of Young modulus, shear modulus, Poisson ratio and internal friction/damping, up to 1600 °C. Working atmosphere: inert gas/air. Dilatometer: range 5 mm, resolution LVDT 100 nm, Temperature resolution 0.1 °C.
Drop-dart Fractovis plus (Instron – ITW)	Maximum velocity: 24 m/s. Maximum Energy: 1800 J. Maximum weight: 70 kg.
ODISI 6100 - Optical Distributed Sensor Interrogator	Optical distributor sensor up to 20m that can be used for the temperature and strain monitoring of coupons or components.
Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy with EDX and EBSD (Mira – Tescan)
Torsion test equipment	Torsion test equipment (160Q Universal torsion test machine - Test Resources, USA) Static torque: from 2 Nm to 500 Nm Test temperature: up to 800°C
Tests equipment for composite materials	Anti-buckling compression tests Shear tests Flexural tests Double cantilever beam test End notched flexural test

3.3.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The research activity carried out in Space4You will define a methodology for the optimization of the plasma treatments aimed at increasing the mechanical performance of composite materials. MAM-MT will work on the mechanical characterization and optimization of the plasma treatment of composite materials and prove the effectiveness of the plasma treatment in space applications. The activity matches the scope of Space4You related to sustainability. Plasma treatment is a sustainable source used to increase the wettability and the adhesion properties between matrix and fibers compared to the chemical baths that are harmful to workers and environmentally unsustainable. The main scope of this activity is to determine optimal plasma treatment process parameters in the initial phase that will be followed by an in-situ treatment methodology with subsequent manufacturing of the final component. Good control of the surface treatment phase and production phase allow for obtaining composite materials with fewer defects and more homogenous mechanical properties.

3.3.4 Foreseen research collaborations

MAM-MT will collaborate with DISAT and ENVIPARK units to define a scientific methodology for plasma-treating composite materials. The DIMEAS unit will work on the mechanical characterization to prove the effectiveness of the plasma treatment by using standard (e.g., double cantilever beam tests and end-notched flexural tests) and non-standard (nano-indentations) testing procedures. The ENVIPARK unit will carry out spectroscopic chemical-physical characterization tests, and in particular, FTIR-ATR and micro-Raman spectroscopic characterization methods to analyze the surface chemical state of the fibres. On the other hand,

The DISAT unit will investigate the surface of the fiber after treatment with optical analysis and with the Z Potential method. This last method will provide information on the surface charge of fibre fabrics, i.e., ionized surface charges, which can influence the mechanical and adhesive properties of the fabrics. All these competencies and facilities will be used to define the treatment methodology that can be adopted for structural materials.

3.4 POLITO-DIMEAS (STAR)

3.4.1 Group description

The Systems and Technologies for Aerospace Research (STAR) team is a research group in the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering involved in space activities since 2003. The team provides expertise in the areas of aerospace missions and systems design, methodologies to support the design and verification of GNC systems, and development of small space platforms and end-to-end missions.

Regarding the activity on nanosatellites, all phases in the lifecycle are addressed, from the design to the assembly-integration-verification, and operations in orbit. It encompasses the development of relevant technologies and the study of new mission scenarios with formation flight satellites.

Since 2003, PoliTO's STAR group is involved in space research based on very small satellites, including the development of two flight missions (launch 2012 and 2016) in collaboration with ESA and one flight mission in collaboration with ASI (launch 2023). The team led Phases 0/A and B1 of the Space Rider Observer Cube – SROC study. The study was completed by the end of 2022, with successful completion of SRR. The team is participating in the Milani CubeSat development, within the Hera mission, as part of a European consortium led by Tyvak International. The STAR group is also in charge of developing for ESA several CubeSat platforms (6U to 12U form factor) for testing electric propulsion systems. The first fit and functional test campaign has been executed at ESTEC in February 2019, and the integration of the first EP system (Helicon-Plasma Thruster) was completed in 2020. After improvement of the test platform, other test campaigns followed in 2021 and 2022, and the project is still ongoing. The group has been involved in other ESA's initiatives, supported mainly by the General Studies Programme (GSP), to study and develop space missions with CubeSats. PoliTO participated in COPINS selection and has been selected for the Multi-purpose Cubesat at the ISS (CubISSat), and LUCE (MoonCARE) studies. PoliTO's STAR group has also been involved in CubeSat related research projects with the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and with the Jet Propulsion Laboratory.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

1. Stesina, F., Corpino, S., Novara, C., Russo, S., *Docking Manoeuvre Control for CubeSats* (2022) *Journal of the Astronautical Sciences*, 69(2), pp. 312-334
2. Stesina, F., Corpino, S., Bosch Borrás, E., Gonzalez Del Amo, J., Pavarin, D., Bellomo, N., Trezzolani, F., *Environmental test campaign of a 6U CubeSat Test Platform equipped with an ambipolar plasma thruster* (2022) *Advances in Aircraft and Spacecraft Science*, Volume 9(3), pp. 195-215
3. Corpino S., Stesina F., *Inspection of The Cis-Lunar Station Using Multi-Purpose Autonomous Cubesats* (2020) *Acta Astronautica*, Volume 175, pp. 591-605
4. Corpino S., Stesina, F., Calvi D., Guerra L., *Trajectory analysis of a CubeSat mission for the inspection of an orbiting vehicle* (2020) *Advances in Aircraft and Spacecraft Science*, Volume 7(3), pp. 745-755
5. Franchi, L., Feruglio, L., Mozzillo, R., Corpino, S., *Model predictive and reallocation problem for CubeSat fault recovery and attitude control* (2018) *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* Volume 98(C), pp. 1034-1055
6. Corpino S., Nichele F., *An Ilities-Driven Methodology for the Analysis of Gaps of Stakeholders Needs in Space Systems Conceptual Design* (2017) *IEEE Systems Journal*, Volume 11(4), pp 2182-2191
7. Feruglio L., Corpino S., *Neural networks to increase the autonomy of interplanetary nanosatellite missions* (2017) *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, Volume 93, pp 52-60
8. Corpino S. et al., *Thermal design and analysis of a nanosatellite in low earth orbit* (2015) *Acta Astronautica*, Volume 115(13), pp247-261
9. Corpino S., Stesina F., *Verification of a CubeSat via Hardware-in-the-loop Simulation* (2014) *EEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, Volume 50(4), pp. 2807-2818

10. Viscio M.A., Corpino S., Stesina, F., Viola N., Circi C., Fumenti M., Fineschi S., Interplanetary CubeSats system for space weather evaluations and technology demonstration (2014) Acta Astronautica, Volume 104(2), pp 516-525

Selected project of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- **Space Rider Observer Cube (SROC) Phase 0/A and B1**- project funded by ESA (2018-2022)
- **Milani Cubesat in the Hera Mission** - project funded by ESA (2020-present)
- **Test Platform for Cubesat Propulsion Systems** (multiple contracts) - projects funded by ESA (2017-present)
- **Global GNSS Interference Monitoring and Notification to Key Operators from Space (GINKO)** – project funded by ESA (2021-22)
- **Lunar Cubesats for Exploration** – LUCE (MoonCARE) - study funded by ESA (2017)
- **Multi-purpose Cubesat at the ISS (CubISSat)** - study funded by ESA (2016-2017)
- **Telecom for Interplanetary CubeSat mission at Mars** - study funded by NASA/JPL (2016)
- **CubeSat for Space Exploration: a new paradigm for Planetary Science Missions**, with Massachusetts Institute of Technology within the Project for the Internationalization of Research funded by the Compagnia di San Paolo Foundation (2013-2015)
- **e-st@r-I and e-st@r-II CubeSat flight missions** of Politecnico di Torino within the FYS! Programme of ESA (2013-present)
- **Spei Satelles flight mission** – funded by ASI (2023 - ongoing)

3.4.2 Facilities

The (STAR) team operates in the **Systems and Technologies for Aerospace Research Laboratory (STARlab)**, a laboratory at the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering of PoliTO. The STARlab is devoted to support education and research initiatives in the area of systems engineering. In the last decade, STARlab has been mainly used to develop **small spacecraft** such as nanosatellites, as well as equipment for larger platforms, mainly for **technology demonstration** space missions. STARlab is the main laboratory used by the CubeSat and Diana Student Teams of Politecnico di Torino. The laboratory offers expertise and services in the areas of:

- Aerospace missions and systems design
- Space systems Assembly and Integration
- Functional verification
- Technology development

Main facilities in the STARlab are:

- Concurrent Engineering System (CES)
- CubeSat Advanced Simulator & Test-bench (CAST)
- CubeSat Control Centre (C3)
- Educational Satellite (ESAT)
- Frictionless Table
- Clean Room (CR1)
- Laminar Flow Bench

In the last decade, STARlab supported the development of several projects, with a total turnover higher than 2 MEUR. The capabilities of the renovated facility make STARlab an excellence in the framework of university laboratories for CubeSat missions and platforms development. Improving the research activity and collaboration with the industry are key elements in the STARlab development roadmap in the long-term horizon.

3.4.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The research activity to be carried out in the Space4You project aims at improving some of the tools already in use within the STARlab. In particular, the work will address the following tools:

- **Concurrent Requirement Analysis and Management System (CREAMS)** – tool for developing and managing requirements. The tool is built onto the Valispace data-driven software, which is interfaced with the Capella MBSE tool where the mission is modelled and analysed.
- **Multi stakeholder NEgoTiation space exploration (MONET)** – tool for supporting model-based concurrent design, which is used for developing and assessing the concepts for the missions, and for supporting trade-off studies wherever needed.
- **CubeSat Advanced Simulator & Test-bench (CAST)** – tool/facility for the simulation of small platforms, which is used for supporting trajectory design, illumination analysis, GNC analysis, and payload simulation.

3.4.4 *Foreseen research collaborations*

The collaboration of the STAR team with other research groups at PoliTO is already ongoing, specifically with:

- NavSAS at PoliTO/DET, on studies of small satellite missions for monitoring interference sources in the GNSS bandwidths from space (GINKO project), and on GNC systems for proximity operations in space (SROC flight mission)
- CAD at PoliTO/DAUIN, on interplanetary nanosatellite missions (MILANI flight mission)

The same projects mentioned above involve a number of companies that could join the Space4You ecosystem. Collaboration with UNITO can be also explored on trajectory design and optimisation to be included in the CAST facility.

On top of this, contacts are already in place with other companies and with the Italian Space Agency for collaboration on specific topics related to the development of key technologies for small satellites.

3.5 POLITO-DISMA

3.5.1 *Group description*

The group has a strong expertise in numerical modeling of multiphysics phenomena in complex geometries, through the use of advanced and innovative numerical tools. In particular the group developed a new domain decomposition approach based on the numerical optimization constrained by partial differential equations. Also the group contributed to the advancement of new galerkin schemes allowing the use of polygonal/polyhedral meshes. Such tools have been successfully applied to multi-scale coupled problems in complex domains. The group also has expertise in parametric fitting techniques, iterative methods and kernel-based interpolation/extrapolation algorithms.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Berrone, S., Grappein, D., Scialò, S. A PDE-constrained optimization method for 3D-1D coupled problems with discontinuous solutions (2023) . DOI: 10.1007/s11075-023-01579-w
- [2] Benedetto, M.F., Borio, A., Kyburg, F., Mollica, J., Scialò, S. An arbitrary order Mixed Virtual Element formulation for coupled multi-dimensional flow problems (2022) 391, art. no. 114204, DOI: 10.1016/j.cma.2021.114204
- [3] Berrone, S., Grappein, D., Scialò, S. 3D-1D coupling on non conforming meshes via a three-field optimization based domain decomposition (2022) 448, art. no. 110738, DOI: 10.1016/j.jcp.2021.110738
- [4] Dassi, F., Fumagalli, A., Losapio, D., Scialò, S., Scotti, A., Vacca, G. The mixed virtual element method on curved edges in two dimensions (2021) 386, art. no. 114098, DOI: 10.1016/j.cma.2021.114098

3.5.2 *Facilities*

The group has an HPC cluster located at DISMA.

3.5.3 Outcomes from Space4You

In the context of the Space4You project the DISMA group can help in the development of numerical tools for the simulation and analysis of innovative composite materials, and, more generally, in the numerical simulation of complex phenomena, in the design of new processes and of new structures. Also, mathematical tools can be effectively used for the efficient management of large quantities of data.

3.5.4 Foreseen research collaborations

The DISMA group can be of support in a large variety of activities related to the project, as, for example in simulating the behaviour of new materials, or for data management and analysis.

3.6 POLITO-DET (NavSAS)

3.6.1 Group description

The **Navigation Signal Analysis and Simulation** group is a team of researchers of **Politecnico di Torino (Dept. of Electronics and Telecommunications)** focused on activities in the field of *Global Navigation Satellite Systems* (GNSS) as the Global Positioning System (GPS) and Galileo, as well as new satellite navigation systems based on LEO satellites. The goal of the research activities is to create a strong know-how on signal processing algorithms, hardware and software systems related to positioning receivers as well as the use of positioning information for innovative services and applications. Particular effort devoted to the definition and study of integrated communication and navigation systems, and one of the most relevant research activity of the last few years addresses the design of Nav/Com systems for the space and Moon scenarios.

The team was born from the experience of the Telecommunications Group of Politecnico di Torino, specializing the telecommunication and signal processing expertise in the field of navigation.

The activities are characterized by continuous collaborations with national and international companies and universities. The group, in the past years, focused most of its recent and important research activities on the Galileo Program, by participating to more than 20 GNSS projects funded in the VI and VII Framework Programmes by GSA and EC and to ESA funded activities.

Researchers of the group have also a relevant experience in supporting GSA and EC for project review and technical assessment of research projects.

The main research topics of the NavSAS Group can be, in short, summarized as follows:

- Innovative architectures for navigation receivers with a focus on original processing schemes for the Galileo signals.
- Fully software implementations of receivers' architectures
- Interference detection and mitigation algorithms
- Multipath rejection techniques based on advanced digital processing
- Hybrid positioning based on heterogeneous NAV/COM measurements and integration with INS
- Assisted-GNSS systems and GNSS cooperative positioning
- GNSS signals authentication
- Analysis and design of ranging and navigation signals for new GNSS and LEO-PNT systems;
- Use of Earth-GNSS in the Space Service Volume
- Design of satellite navigation systems for the Moon and for Space Exploration
- Atmospheric and Environmental monitoring via GNSS signals processing

Details on the research activities can be found at <http://www.navsas.polito.it>

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] A. Nardin, J. Fraire, and F. Dovis, "Contact plan design for gnss constellations: A case study with

optical intersatellite links,” IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 1981–1995, 2022. doi: 10.1109/TAES.2021.3135025

- [2] A. Nardin, F. Dovic, and J. A. Fraire, “Empowering the Tracking Performance of LEO-Based Positioning by Means of Meta-Signals,” IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 244–253, 2021. doi: 10.1109/JRFID.2021.3077082
- [3] L. Musumeci, F. Dovic, J. Silva, P. Da Silva, and H. Lopes, “Design of a High Sensitivity GNSS Receiver for Lunar Missions,” Advances in Space Research, vol. 57, no. 11, pp. 2285–2313, 2016. doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2016.03.020

Selected project of the research group relevant to Space4you:

Contract	Start	End	Funding Institution	Coordinator
Lunar Ranging Navigation System	01.10.2021	30.04.2023	European Space Agency	Thales Alenia Space
GINKO-S – Global GNSS Interference Monitoring and Notification to Key Operators from Space	01.07.2021	30.06.2022	European Space Agency	ItalSpazio spa
WEAK GNSS NAVIGATION SIGNAL ON THE MOON	08.11.2012	29.10.2013	European Space Agency	DEIMOS ENGENHARIA SA
Attività di R&S inerente alla Navigazione GNSS nello Space volume Terra /Luna – nell’ambito del Lunar GNSS Receiver Experiment (LuGRE)	01.09.2021	31.08.2024	Italian Space Agency	POLITECNICO DI TORINO
MISW - Mitigation of Space Weather threats to GNSS services	01.02.2014	30.07.2016	European Commission	UNIVERSITY OF BATH

3.6.2 Facilities

The NavSAS Group operates in a Navigation Lab equipped with leading edge facilities for simulation, real signals processing and prototype developments. Furthermore, it can exploit specific tools tailored to research activities.

N-GENE2 is a GPS+Galileo+EGNOS fully software receiver developed by the NavSAS group. N-Gene is able to receive the GPS Coarse Acquisition (C/A) code on L1, with the ability to process a minimum of 12 channels in real time, and track live Galileo GIOVE-A and B signals transmitted on the E1 band. The receiver leverages improved positioning accuracy through the use of differential corrections broadcasted by the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay System (EGNOS) and by EGNOS Data Access Service (EDAS). The 8-bit samples quantization allows for implementing all of those signal processing blocks requiring a fine resolution, as for example notch filters for interference mitigation, pulse blanking or multipath mitigation techniques based on the estimation of the parameters of the received signal. N-Gene is also able to retrieve measurements from an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and combine them at the Position Velocity and Time (PVT) level implementing both a loosely and tight coupling integration of the GPS and INS units.

A non real-time Matlab © version of the N-GENE2 receiver is available for algorithm testing and development. The loss of the real-time processing feature is traded-off with a full flexibility and modularity of the architecture implementation.

This version is already implementing:

- Ionospheric scintillation detection algorithms
- Interference detection and mitigation unit, for continuous wave, jamming, and pulsed interference.

N-FUELS is a signal simulator designed to offer a flexible and complete tool able to reproduce off-line GNSS signals at the ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) output of a navigation receiver, either at intermediate frequency or at baseband. The signal generator can account for the effects of multipath, Doppler, interferences of different nature (i.e., intra-system, inter-system, band-limited, continuous wave, etc...) on all the bands of

interests for the future GNSS, as well as AWGN (Additive White Gaussian Noise) and receiver front-end characteristics (equivalent filter bandwidth, frequency plan, ADC). Thereby, a reliable, though non-real time, simulation of the received signal samples after ADC conversion is made available at a sampling frequency open to the user's setting. This allows the test of any reception algorithm that processes digital samples in a completely controlled signal/environmental scenario (e.g.: acquisition algorithms, code and carriers tracking loops, C/No estimation algorithms, interference or multipath detection and mitigation algorithm)

3.6.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The research work performed in Space4You aims at developing new signals and architectural concepts for the provision of positioning and navigation services on the moon. To this aim new signals formats and modulation are being studied, as well as positioning technique that could be effective in space exploiting both the terrestrial GNSS services (GPS and Galileo) as well as the satellite constellations for the Moon foreseen in the Moonlight program of ESA and in the LunaNET architecture proposed by NASA.

3.6.4 Foreseen research collaborations

On one side a tighter relationship with the other research groups dealing with space activity in the ecosystem is expected. This collaboration will yield to joint research works, and to this aim common research work is already going on with:

- DIMEAS/STAR: study of the use of GNSS and cooperative positioning in space mission, use of small satellites for monitoring of interference sources in the GNSS bandwidths
- DET/TNG: design of ranging and communication links for ICT infrastructures to be used on Moon
- DIST: study of the synergies between the use of Copernicus constellation and Galileo for advanced services from space
- LINKS/ADS: study of LEO GNSS constellations, and interference monitoring

In particular, the collaboration with LINKS-ADS aims at developing the first set-up of an experimental facility where innovative navigation and communication services can be tested.

The cooperation with the companies of the ecosystem is foreseen. On one side this will allow the transfer of the expertise toward the companies involved in the space programs for the Moon, allowing as well the industrial requirements to be taken into account by the research side.

3.7 POLITO-DET (TNG)

3.7.1 Group description

The **Telecommunication Networks Group (TNG)** is a team of researchers of **Politecnico di Torino (Dept. of Electronics and Telecommunications)** focused on activities in the field of telecommunication networks, based on any possible technology (wired, wireless and optical). The group is expert on (i) performance evaluation and analysis of complex network systems, (ii) design and evaluation of network protocols, (iii) optimal network control and resource allocation, (iv) virtualization and cloud computing, (v) 5G and beyond 5G networks, (vi) network programmability. The main peculiarity of the group is the combination between strong expertise on analytical approaches and a consolidated expertise in both simulative and experimental approaches.

The activities are characterized by continuous collaborations with national and international companies and universities.

Details on the research activities can be found at <http://www.telematica.polito.it>

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

[1] Cohen, Itamar; Chiasserini, Carla Fabiana; Giaccone, Paolo; Scalosub, Gabriel, Dynamic Service Provisioning in the Edge-cloud Continuum with Bounded Resources, in: IEEE-ACM TRANSACTIONS ON NETWORKING, 2023

[2] Adeppady, Madhura; Giaccone, Paolo; Karl, Holger; Chiasserini, Carla Fabiana, Reducing Microservices Interference and Deployment Time in Resource-constrained Cloud Systems, in: IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON NETWORK AND SERVICE MANAGEMENT, 2023

[3] Lotfimahyari, Iman; Sviridov, German; Giaccone, Paolo; Bianco, Andrea, Data plane assisted state replication with Network Function Virtualization, in: IEEE SYSTEMS JOURNAL, 2022

Selected projects of the research group relevant to Space4you:

Title	Date	Topic
H2020 5G EVE	2018- 2021	5G EVE is a 5G PPP infrastructure project to provide the European 5G validation platform for extensive trials. CNIT supported the development of the 5G edge node deployed at Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) and implemented a vertical application to detect the people mobility in urban scenario through the WiFi interface of the carried smartphones.
H2020 5G- Transformer	2017- 2019	5G-Transformer defined three novel building blocks that have been developed and demonstrated integrating different vertical industries: (1) the Vertical Slicer as the logical entry point for verticals to support the creation of transport slices, (2) the Service Orchestrator to orchestrate the federation of transport networking and computing resources, and (3) Mobile Transport Platform as the underlying unified transport layer
H2020 5G Growth	2019- 2021	5Growth empower verticals industries (Industry 4.0, Transportation, and Energy) with an AI-driven automated 5G End-to-End platform that allows achieving the services key performance targets. To this end, 5Growth develops an AIML platform for realising the MLaaS concept, and the automated management of network and services over multiple domains and technologies.
H2020 Hexa- X	2020- 2022	Hexa-X enables connected intelligence, networks of networks, sustainability, global service coverage, extreme experience, and trustworthiness for Beyond-5G/6G vision. Within the project, POLITO develops mechanisms for resource assignment in ultra-dense D2D/ D2I scenarios where network densification is foreseen through ubiquitous miniaturized, heterogeneous base stations. POLITO also works on interactions with environment sensors or through wearables, and on AI-based data processing.
H2020 SEMANTIC	2020- 2023	The project develops novel edge-computing network and service solutions for the support of mobile users. POLITO focuses on the design of ML-based schemes for the optimal deployment of micro-services for seamless provisioning of virtualised services to mobile users, while ensuring extremely low delay and high-quality of experience. To this end, it leverages experimental results highlighting resource contention and interference among services co-located in the same server

3.7.2 Facilities

The TNG will exploit the High Performance Computation (HPC) cluster for simulations, available at Politecnico di Torino, with 140 Teraflops computation capabilities. This facility will be crucial to run the simulations for large satellite networks.

3.7.3 Outcomes from Space4You

Satellite networks provides a novel communication paradigm by which satellite communicate and cooperate to send information across different sites on earth. The aim of the work is to consider the intermittent communication between satellite and evaluate the maximum performance (in terms of latency and bandwidth) by exploiting a store-carry-forward approach. A time-space graph model of the communication will be devised,

and a numerical solver will be developed to evaluate the performance for a large network of cooperative satellites.

The proposed approach will be compared with state-of-the-art simulation tools and models, as OpenSAND¹ and OpenC3², to understand the approach with the best tradeoff between scalability and accuracy. Notably, scalability is a crucial requirement due to the large number of cooperative satellites in a constellation.

3.7.4 Foreseen research collaborations

The research activity is focused on telecommunication networks but it requires the interaction with experts in the field of satellite communications and orbits/trajectories. The main expected collaboration will be with POLITO-DET (NavSAS) and with Space@UniTo.

3.8 POLITO-DIST

3.8.1 Group description

POLITO@DIST is a research group pertaining to the geomatics sector which carries out its activities mainly in the applications of Earth observation. This includes both the use of data acquired from satellite and aerial platforms, enabling the enhancement of the 3D component and the use of artificial intelligence algorithms for extracting added value information from the data. Funded projects include grants from the ITC Committee for the development of expertise in the field of operational implementation of Digital Twins; active participation in the "Geoscience IR" project, financed with PNRR funds and coordinated by ISPRA, various projects financed by SITI and Links related to the valorization of spatial downstream assets, as well as national projects (Prin from 2012 to 2022) on research lines related to environmental monitoring and the use of innovative geomatics tools for applications in the field of urban mobility. In 2023, the research group will be responsible for the implementation of an urban Digital Twin through a specific agreement with the City of Turin.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Fissore, V., Bovio, L., Perotti, L., Boccardo, P., Borgogno-Mondino, E. "Towards a Digital Twin Prototype of Alpine Glaciers: Proposal for a Possible Theoretical Framework", *Remote Sensing*, 2023, 15(11), 2844
- [2] Dell'anna, S., Mansueto, G., Boccardo, P., Arco, E., "Multi-spectral sensors monitoring of the epidemic of Xylella Fastidiosa in the Apulia Region" *MELECON 2022 - IEEE Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference, Proceedings*, 2022, pp. 610–615
- [3] Ajmar, A., Arco, E., Boccardo, P., , "Definition of a methodology to derive road network functional hierarchy classes using car tracking data", *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives* [this link is disabled](#), 2020, 43(B4), pp. 307–312
- [4] Mansueto, G., Boccardo, P., Ajmar, A., "Satellite Stereo Data Comprehensive Benchmark for DSM Extraction", *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2020, 12252 LNCS, pp. 858–873
- [5] Brovelli, M.A., Boccardo, P., Bordogna, G., ...Munafò, M., Pirotti, F. "URBAN GEO BIG DATA", *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives*, 2019, 42(4/W14), pp. 23–30

3.8.2 Facilities

The research group gather at SDG11lab owing its name to the Sustainable Development Goal 11 of the United Nations 2030 Agenda: "Make human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable". The laboratory consists of an infrastructure aimed at the production of complex spatial information, which uses resources

¹ <https://www.opensand.org/>

² <https://openc3.com/>

dedicated to artificial intelligence, access to satellite big data and, at the same time, which favors an open source policy to reach users with different levels of specialization. The SDG11lab explores the scientific processes regarding the physical structures of the planet and the impact of human settlements on the world. Specialized equipment allows us to collect data from image and documentary sources using aerial and satellite remote sensing and analyze it through geographic information systems. The laboratory infrastructure therefore allows the production of value-added spatial information, guaranteeing:

- efficient access to cartographic, satellite and in-situ data;
- the development and implementation of analytical tools in various application fields.

The architecture involves the use of hardware solutions such as cloud computing and resources dedicated to artificial intelligence, while granting access to satellite big data, programming frameworks and the use of open source and commercial software aimed at users with different levels of specialization.

3.8.3 Outcomes from Space4You

POLITO@DIST within this project aims to implement a high-resolution 3D model of urban areas that can be used for the implementation of thematic digital twins, paying particular attention to energy applications (efficiency, transition and energy communities), emergency management (especially urban floods resulting from concentrated heavy rainfall) and territorial planning (creation of new urban plans)

3.8.4 Foreseen research collaborations

POLITO@DIST is already carrying out joint research initiatives with the ENERGY@POLITO group, collaborates with the Links foundation and Ithaca Srl and will soon carry out joint activities with the Urban Lab Association of the City of Turin and Compagnia di San Paolo. The first contacts then began to proceed to a specific research agreement with South Wales University, Sydney, Australia for the development and implementation of urban digital twins.

3.9 POLITO-DAUIN (CAD & GRAINS)

3.9.1 Group description

The POLITO@DAUIN team involves researchers from the CAD (Electronic CAD & Reliability group) and the GRAINS (GRAphics and INTelligent Systems) groups. The CAD group is expert in the design of hardware and software solutions for the validation of safety critical systems and the design of architectures (at different implementation levels) resilient to faults occurrences induced by defect on manufacturing or radiation phenomena, from single and multiple event effects. The group is also active in the development of radiation test setups for various type of technology, device and effects and experimental execution of radiation test campaigns. The group is in contact with different facilities in Europe and USA: UCL (Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium), PSI (Villigen, Switzerland), GANIL (Caen, France), ISIS (Didcot, UK) and Los Alamos (USA). The GRAINS group, on the other hand, has expertise in the design, training and implementation of deep neural networks, with applications in particular to image analysis and interpretation. The complementary strengths of the two groups will contribute specifically to the design and development of modern, performant and resilient computing platforms for on board satellites, including platforms designed for deep learning systems, tackling all aspects in a synergistic fashion.

Selected publications of the research groups relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Ruospo, A., Gavarini, G., De Sio, C., Guerrero, J., Sterpone, L., Reorda, M. S., ... & Athavale, J. (2023, April). Assessing convolutional neural networks reliability through statistical fault injections. In *2023 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [2] De Sio, C., Azimi, S., & Sterpone, L. (2022). FireNN: Neural networks reliability evaluation on hybrid platforms. *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, *10*(2), 549-563.
- [3] Portaluri, Andrea, et al. "On the Reliability of Real-Time Operating System on Embedded Soft Processor for Space Applications." *International Conference on Architecture of Computing Systems*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022.

- [4] Bozzoli, L., Catanese, A., Fazzoletto, E., Scarpa, E., Goehringer, D., Pertuz, S. A., ... & King, S. (2023, April). EuFRATE: European FPGA Radiation-hardened Architecture for Telecommunications. In *2023 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [5] Sterpone, L., Luoni, F., Azimi, S., & Du, B. (2020). A 3-D simulation-based approach to analyze heavy ions-induced SET on digital circuits. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 67(9), 2034-2041.

3.9.2 Facilities

The research activities will exploit computing and hardware infrastructure already available to the research groups involved in addition to hardware acquired within the project. Further investigations will be done on resilient and accelerated computation exploiting the European Radiation-Hardened BRAVE computing platform for deep space.

3.9.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The research will strengthen the lab competences and capabilities and generate assets both at the software and hardware level. The targeted algorithmic advances, that will be implemented in the form of libraries to be used for the training and evaluation of deep neural networks, can be exploited transversally to build DL-enhanced modules at both operation and exploitation phases. In particular, POLITO@DAUIN will investigate applications within the context of Earth Observation. POLITO@DAUIN will investigate the adoption of innovative resilient computing architectures able to integrate self-correction and mitigation techniques together with on-site reconfigurable capabilities that will target high performance computation in space. Furthermore, the investigation will include the preparation of a prototype of a computing architecture based on Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) and General-Purpose Graphic Processing Units (GPGPUs) compliant with the Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) radiation environment and eventually suitable for deep-space and long duration missions.

3.9.4 Foreseen research collaborations

The proposed research activities are the result of a new collaboration established between the CAD and GRAINS group, resulting in the activation of a jointly supervised PhD scholarship.

3.10 POLITO-DISEG

3.10.1 Group description

The research group at DISEG will focus on the development of building systems through additive manufacturing processes with particular attention to the structural form finding and parametric design (optimization) (ArtIStE research group). The research unit PoliTo will offer, for the form finding phase, the innovation of design phase solutions by optimization procedures put in relation to specific structural parameters. In particular, the know-how of the research group models will be implemented through codes belonging to the field of dynamic simulation and assembly processes. We will proceed in this sense through the use of a unique virtual environment (MSC.v4ND) able to simulate both the dynamics of interconnected rigid bodies (structural form finding) subject to reduced gravity, and to analyze, through physical-based animations, the tests of the different systems of production and assembly of the structure. Through the research group Artificial-intelligence-based approaches will be used as alternatives for efficiently solving problems in Space habitats. Evolutionary and metaheuristic computation, neural networks, fuzzy systems, expert systems, classification, regression, and learning will be used in structural optimization and in structural monitoring of space architecture models.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Jonathan Melchiorre, Amedeo Manuello, Francesco Marmo, Sigrid Adriaenssens, Giuseppe Carlo Marano. "Differential formulation and numerical solution for elastic arches with variable curvature and tapered cross-sections". *Europ. J. of Mech. Solids A*, (2022). Vol. 97, (2023) 104757.

[2] Valentina Sumini, Marta Rossi, Amedeo Manuello, “A Sustainability by Design lesson learned from Space” Proceedings of the IWSS 2023 Turin, June 2023. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering – Springer.

[3] Andrea Manuello, Amedeo Manuello, Giuseppe Carlo Marano, “Adaptive Structures with Intrinsic Control: Exploratory Habitation-Vehicles for Space Environment” Proceedings of the IWSS 2023 Turin, June 2023. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering – Springer.

[4] M. Rosso, Raffaele Cucuzza, Fabio Di Trapani, Giuseppe C. Marano, "Nonpenalty Machine Learning Constraint Handling Using PSO-SVM for Structural Optimization", Advances in Civil Engineering, vol. 2021, Article ID 6617750, 17 pages, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6617750>

3.10.2 Facilities

Providing and use of a workstation devoted to the implementation of the project activities: structural optimization of space structures and habitat modules with innovative methods and the use of artificial intelligence. In addition to the hardware acquired for the project, the research activities will make use of the computational and hardware infrastructure already available for the research group and devoted to optimization problem solutions. Reduced scale models in physical similarity, realized also by 3D-printers acquires ad hoc for the project, respecting the characterizing a-dimensional parameters will be realized. The tests will be validated in the analyzing the critical collapse conditions using acoustic emission (AE) and Digital-Image-Correlation (DIC) techniques. In particular, 3D DIC device already at the group's disposal will be adopted in the experimental validations.

3.10.3 Outcomes from Space4You

After the definition of the additive technology, and its implementation on materials simulating the composition of the extraterrestrial soil, the DisegPolito research group will deal with the quantification of the mechanical properties of the molded components through mechanical characterization tests. The set-up of the characterization tests will be defined ad-hoc on the meso-structure of the parts, and will therefore consider their nature isotropic, orthotropic or anisotropic, as a function of the production process. This evaluation will allow the definition of the constitutive model of the material, an crucial formulation of the mechanical behavior by means of FEA (Finite Element Analysis) of structures and infrastructures for extra-earth habitat employments. Additionally the research group is defining the collaboration for the scientific and technical support for the planning and preliminary design of the first italian “SpacePort” that is going to be located at the airport of Grottaglie (Italy)

3.10.4 Foreseen research collaborations

The suggested research initiatives are the product of an innovative partnership formed between the ArtIStE research group and the Princeton University. In addition, the research activity is the subject of a collaboration between PoliTo-Diseg and the MIT Media Lab within Space Exploration Initiative and Responsive Environments.

Moreover, there are ongoing activities with the Diseg and Aeroporti di Puglia for the scientific support in preliminary spaceport planning in the location of Grottaglie (Italy)

3.11 POLITO-DIGEP

3.11.1 Group description

The research conducted at the Center DIGEP@Polito revolves around the development of a comprehensive framework that explores the dynamics of innovation and entrepreneurship. A particular focus is placed on applying best practices and novel ideas within the local ecosystem. The Center adopts a systemic approach to studying the innovation process. In this regard, the research endeavors extend beyond examining the characteristics of innovative start-ups alone. They also delve into the roles played by various stakeholders, such as large corporations, financial institutions, regulatory bodies, universities, public research centers, and incubators. These entities collectively shape the environmental conditions of local entrepreneurial ecosystems.

The Center is engaged in several key research topics that can be summarized as follows:

Understanding Innovation Dynamics: The Center aims to gain insights into the intricate dynamics of innovation by exploring how ideas are generated, developed, and transformed into tangible products, services, or processes. This includes studying the factors that facilitate or hinder innovation within local contexts.

Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Analysis: The research activities focus on comprehending the complex network of interactions among different actors in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. This involves assessing the contributions of various stakeholders and how they influence the overall environment for entrepreneurship.

Best Practices and Knowledge Transfer: The Center examines successful strategies and best practices in innovation and entrepreneurship. It explores how these practices can be effectively transferred and applied within the local ecosystem to foster the growth and success of start-ups.

3.11.2 Facilities

The DIGEP Centre will be able to support Space4you activities thanks to its extensive network and opportunities. The Centre will collaborate with I3P - the Turin Polytechnic's Business Incubator, and with the European Space Agency's Business Incubation Centre in Turin (ESABIC Turin), which supports new space initiatives operating in both the upstream and downstream segments of space and has gathered a very wide network of supporting firms, research center, financial operators and investment funds. Moreover, through his lines of activity, the Center aims to contribute to the understanding and advancement of innovation and entrepreneurship, providing valuable insights and guidance for both researchers and practitioners in the field.

3.11.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The Center aims to gain insights into the intricate dynamics of innovation by exploring how ideas are generated, developed, and transformed into tangible products, services, or processes. This includes studying the factors that facilitate or hinder innovation within local contexts.

3.11.4 Foreseen research collaborations

The center will collaborate with the other research groups involved in the SPACE4YOU project by supporting them in identifying the key factors concerning both the new business opportunities generated by technological change and the dynamics of localized interaction between the various players in the innovation ecosystem.

3.12 Advanced Computing, Photonics & Electromagnetics (LINKS-CPE)

3.12.1 Group description

LINKS-CPE works actively in the context of High Performance Computing (HPC), with a specific focus on the analysis and development of innovative approach for orchestration and simulation of complex models. Research activities include innovative computing domains, like “computing continuum” and “quantum computing”, aiming at fostering the integration between hardware and software on high performance computing and communication. These technologies can be applied to several application domains, however, they are specifically adapted to support the research in the aerospace domain thanks to the capacity to provide simulation and data analysis tools able to build digital twin models of complex systems. The main research can be summarized as follows:

- Innovative orchestration approaches for high performance computing.
- Architectural models to exploit the potentialities of RISC-V processors.
- Digital twin models based on satellite or drone images.
- Edge computing algorithms to support the development of AI algorithms.

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

[1] Savio, P; Scionti, A; Vitali, G; Viviani, P; Vercellino, C; Terzo, O; Nguyen, Hn; Magarielli, D; Spano, E; Marconcini, M; Poli, F. Accelerating legacy applications with spatial computing devices / - In: THE JOURNAL OF SUPERCOMPUTING. - ISSN 0920-8542. (2022). [<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-022-04925-2>]

[2] Vercellino, C; Scionti, A; Varavallo, G; Viviani, P; Vitali, G; Terzo, O. A machine learning approach for an HPC use case: The jobs queuing time prediction / - In: FUTURE GENERATION COMPUTER SYSTEMS. - ISSN 0167-739X. - 143:(2023), pp. 215-230. [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2023.01.020>]

[3] Scionti A., Viviani, P., Vitali, G., Vercellino, C., & Terzo, O. (2022). Enabling the HPC and Artificial Intelligence Cross-Stack Convergence at the Exascale Level. In *HPC, Big Data, and AI Convergence Towards Exascale* (pp. 37–58). <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003176664-3>

[4] Vercellino, C; Viviani, P; Vitali, G; Scionti, A; Scarabosio, A; Terzo, O; Giusto, E; Montrucchio, B. Neural-powered unit disk graph embedding: qubits connectivity for some QUBO problems / - (2022), pp. 186-196. IEEE International Conference on Quantum Computing and Engineering (QCE22) Broomfield, CO (USA) September 18–23, 2022) [<https://doi.org/10.1109/QCE53715.2022.00038>].

Selected projects of the research group relevant to Space4you:

LEXIS	The aim of the LEXIS project was to give a strong emphasis and advance for optimizing processing of very large datasets in heterogenous environment for edge to Data Centres. Industrial pilots (including the simulation of design of aeronautics components) and E-Science pilots were considered in a computing continuum perspective, covering the integration of HPC, Bigdata and Cloud technologies and approaches to full exploit their potential.
ACROSS	The ACROSS project will build an advanced engineering platform for HPC and data centric environment. Cloud and new data nodes technologies with Burst Buffer around pre-exascale and Petascale infrastructure will leverage large-scale industrial applications from existing HPC infrastructure, employing Big Data analytics solutions and augment them with Cloud services. One of the main characteristic is an efficient use of HPC clusters and Heterogeneous architecture (GPU + FPGA). LINKS-CPE is the coordinator of ACROSS.
VITAMIN-V	The project contributions towards the adoption of open processing architectures (RISC-V based such as the European Processor Initiative) in cloud computing will be on the interfacing of hardware processing components to critical software layers components essential to virtualization. The hardware components will include RISC-V CPUs and also domain specific accelerators built on RISC-V extensions. The software layer components will include hypervisors (virtual machine monitors) for RISC-V CPUs and accelerators, as well as higher-level virtualization components of different granularities (containers, classic virtual machines) to support both the established cloud virtualization approaches and emerging ones such as serverless cloud computing. The interfacing of the software layers components to the underlying RISC-V hardware components will be architected to deliver critical features required in cloud computing: performance (quality-of-service) of the cloud services (by minimal virtualization overheads), security and trustworthiness of the application software layers (through isolation features and encryption), reliable execution despite hardware issues (through system monitoring). The evaluation of all different aspects of the virtualization stack will be realized in a comprehensive virtual and real system setup and will include: emulation (RISC-V support on QEMU), cycle accurate simulation (RISC-V modeling and measurements on gem5), and real hardware implementation (RISC-V implementations on FPGAs).
VIS4BEER	The VIS4BEER project aims to operate in the Industry 4.0 technological context to improve the efficiency of the manufacturing process by means of smart sensors. The

	main idea is to combine edge-computing and artificial intelligence to evaluate the potential benefit of such an approach in a manufacturing context compared to a traditional approach.
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3.12.2 Facilities

LINKS-CPE is able to support the research activities of the SPACE4YOU project with:

- A server stack located in LINKS premises where HPC approaches can be developed and tested to promote the development of simulation and digital twin models.
- A set of Edge Nodes based on the Nvidia Jetson Xavier platform to develop and test AI-based solutions.
- Capability to access HPC clusters to get resources for simulations and implementing a full digital twin model.
- A HW Laboratory for rapid prototyping, to support the development of innovative hardware solutions.

3.12.3 Outcomes from Space4You

In the framework of the SPACE4YOU, LINKS-CPE carries out activities related to the development of a twin model based on data and images coming from Earth observation by a satellite or a constellation of satellites. In order to make the digital twin as equivalent as possible to reality, a great amount of data needs to be elaborated, thus requiring the adoption of high-performance computing approaches. At the same time, the integration of AI algorithms with the edge computing paradigm will help to increase the resilience of systems as well as the capabilities to process and adapt their behaviors to external inputs.

3.12.4 Foreseen research collaborations

LINKS-CPE will collaborate to the other research group involved in the SPACE4YOU project by supporting them in simulating and testing innovative approaches for the aerospace sector. In particular, in collaboration with the research groups dedicated to earth observation based on satellite imagery will be the basis for the development of proper algorithms able to elaborate data according to high performance computing approaches. Moreover, proper simulation tools can be jointly designed to support the development of innovative solutions.

3.13 Artificial Intelligence, Data and Space (LINKS-ADS)

3.13.1 Group description

The LINKS Artificial Intelligence, Data and Space (ADS) team leverages the combined power of Artificial Intelligence and Data, with a particular emphasis on data obtained from satellite systems, to tackle several research topics, including:

- Integration of Artificial Intelligence and Data in digital applications for addressing; industrial and societal challenges;
- Utilization of geospatial data received from remote and in-field systems;
- Advanced data processing through the use of algorithms;
- Creation of effective and usable human-to-machine interfaces;
- Implementation and operationalization of Deep learning algorithms;
- Creation of intelligent applications that work symbiotically with humans;
- AI applications include advanced web search engines, recommendation systems, language understanding, vision, self-driving cars, and strategic game systems.

Over the years, the LINKS-ADS team also worked on new technologies and systems related to space, with focus on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). The investigated topics can be grouped into three main research lines:

- Space-related core technologies: GNSS signal processing, Software Defined Radio (SDR) developments, integration with sensors and terrestrial technologies, Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) applications, signals for command and control of TLC satellites

- Downlink applications: use of new signals and enhanced messages in specific domains, Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) positioning in constrained environments, antennas and receivers field tests, GNSS-based passive radar for remote sensing
- Satellite-based critical systems: analysis, mitigation and countermeasures for unintentional and intentional interference, design of new Galileo civilian signals with authentication features (cryptography)

Selected publications of the research group relevant to Space4you:

- [1] E. Falletti, M. T. Gamba and M. Pini, "Design and Analysis of Activation Strategies for Adaptive Notch Filters to Suppress GNSS Jamming," in *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 3718-3734, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAES.2020.2982301
- [2] Troglia Gamba, M.; Nicola, M.; Motella, B. Computational Load Analysis of a Galileo OSNMA-Ready Receiver for ARM-Based Embedded Platforms. *Sensors* **2021**, *21*, 467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21020467>
- [3] Cucchi, L., Damy, S., Paonni, M., Nicola, M., Gamba, M. Troglia, Motella, B., Fernandez-Hernandez, I., "Assessing Galileo OSNMA Under Different User Environments by Means of a Multi-Purpose Test Bench, Including a Software-defined GNSS Receiver," *Proceedings of the 34th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation (ION GNSS+ 2021)*, St. Louis, Missouri, September 2021, pp. 3653-3667. <https://doi.org/10.33012/2021.17966>
- [4] E. Arnaudo, A. Tavera, C. Masone, F. Dominici and B. Caputo, "Hierarchical Instance Mixing Across Domains in Aerial Segmentation," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 13324-13333, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3243475.
- [5] F. Montello, E. Arnaudo and C. Rossi, "MMFlood: A Multimodal Dataset for Flood Delineation From Satellite Imagery," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 96774-96787, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3205419.

Selected projects of the research group relevant to Space4you:

Project #1	<i>GINKO-S – GNSS Interference monitoring and Notification to Key Operators from Space</i>
Funded by	ESA Contract No. 4000134889/21/NL/MP/mk (Subcontractor to Italspazio s.r.l.)
Duration	2021-2023
Summary	<p>The main aim of the project is to study, design and develop a GNSS interference detection and localization system from LEO satellite, cubesat (or microsatellite), to demonstrate the validity of the concept of interference detection on a large scale and on areas not covered by systems earthlings.</p> <p>LINKS-ADS was in charge of implementing GNSS interference detection algorithms on a space-enabled Single-Board Computer (SBC) and performing functional tests in the laboratory before payload integration.</p>
Project #2	<i>PATHFINDER – PNT as A Technology to support drones' BVLOS scenarios for preventive monitoring and FIrst RespoNDER missions</i>
Funded by	ESA Contract No. 4000135297/21/NL/MP/mk (Subcontractor to Sistemica s.p.a)
Duration	2021-2023
Summary	<p>The main aim of the project is to design, develop and validate a navigation payload for drones operating in BVLOS (Behind Visual Line Of Sight) scenarios for civil protection purposes. The project mainly focuses on some technological elements, which introduce innovative aspects with respect to the state of the art.</p>

LINKS-ADS was in charge of developing algorithms for the advanced hybridization of GNSS and Inertial Navigation System (INS) and calculating the positioning solution integrity. LINKS-ADS implemented the Proof-Of-Concept (PoC) on SBC that integrates a dual-frequency OSNMA-enabled consumer grade GNSS receiver and is hosted aboard an aerial drone.

Project #3 *ROOT – Rolling Out OSNMA for the secure synchronization of telecom networks*

Funded by EUSPA, Grant Agreement 101004261 (H2020-SPACE-EGNSS-2019-2020)

Duration 2020-2022

Summary The project has as its main objective the evaluation of the advantages introduced by Galileo's OSNMA signal in the synchronization of networks, mainly in terms of greater resilience to intentional interference and cyberattacks. ROOT followed an experimental approach to demonstrate and measure the increased level of robustness provided by (1) OSNMA-ready pre-commercial Galileo receivers and (2) secure network synchronization distribution methods via Precision Time Protocol (PTP).

LINKS-ADS was in charge of the coordination, and the leadership of the Dissemination/Communication and Conclusions and Lesson Learnt work packages.

Project #4 *SAFERS– Structured Approaches for Forest fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies*

Funded by EC, Grant Agreement 869353 (H2020-SC5-2018-2019-2020)

Duration 2020-2024

Summary The project proposes to realize a comprehensive Emergency Management System (EMS) named SAFE. It will act along the key phases of the emergency management cycle, coupling information from Earth Observation (EO) data and services offered by Copernicus and Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), crowdsourced data from social media and from specific applications that can be used by both citizens as well as from in-field professional agents, data generated by accurate sensors to detect smoke or fires. Advanced algorithm based on Artificial Intelligence will be used to generate risk maps and early warnings in the preparedness phase, estimate the forest fire extension and its propagation in function of the forecasted weather and soil conditions in the response phase, compute the impacts of an extinguished fire in terms of economic losses and monitor the soil recovery in the post-event phase. LINKS-ADS focuses on:

- Coordination
- Crowdsourcing (inc. Drones and cameras reports), data fusion and analysis with Machine Learning
- Deep learning models for the burned area recognition from Copernicus data

Project #5 *ATLANTIS– Improved resilience of Critical Infrastructures Against Large scale transNational and sysTemic rISks*

Funded by European REA, Grant Agreement 1010739 (HORIZON-CL3-2021-INFRA-01)

Duration 2022-2025

Summary The project aims at enhancing resilience and Cyber-Physical-Human (CPH) security of the key European Critical Infrastructures (CIs) ECIs, going beyond the scope of distinct assets, systems, and single CI, by addressing resilience at the systemic level against major natural hazards and complex attacks that could potentially disrupt vital functions of the society.

LINKS-ADS focuses on activities on 2nd generation Galileo signals for critical infrastructure protection, AI applied to EGNSS navigation signals for new analysis methods and AI applied to multimodal datasets.

3.13.2 Facilities

The LINKS-ADS research team offers a multi-node computing cluster with combined resources that amount to a total of more than 300 individual CPU cores, more than 1.5TB of RAM, more than 70TB of hardware storage, and around 400GB of GPU memory for CUDA-enabled parallel processing. The hardware is mainly utilized for high-performance computation, including deep learning, with dedicated resources for the testing and the deployment of the devised models and related services. The team has a consolidated experience in the training and implementation of machine learning models, grounded on a development stack that includes frameworks such as Pytorch, Tensorflow or Keras for deep learning tasks, Python libraries such as FastAPI for the fast prototyping of Application Programming Interfaces (API), and tools such as Docker for an easier deployment in different configurations.

The LINKS-ADS team has also a lab devoted to radio navigation technologies and applications, where the following equipment, instruments and research tools are available:

- RF GNSS signal generator: IFEN NavX NCS (Navigation Constellation Simulator), see Figure 3-1 (a), including settings for the generation of intermediate spoofing attacks.
- NGene2: Custom real time GNSS software radio receiver, accepting signals from different RF front-ends and tracking live GPS, EGNOS, and Galileo signals. It can be executed on general purpose PCs or on ARM-based embedded platforms;
- Different types of GNSS RF front ends (i.e.: commercial and prototypes, single- and multi-bits, single- and multi-frequency);
- Atomic clocks (rubidium standards) and stable timing references;
- Different types of commercial GNSS antennas (passive/active, single/multi bands);
- Survey-grade and high-end GNSS receivers, from different manufacturers, namely Septentrio SA, NovAtel Inc, TopCon Inc. – Figure 3-1 (b);
- Consumer-grade GNSS receivers, from different manufacturers, namely ublox, NVS, ST-microelectronics;
- Commercial bit grabbers and RF play back systems, e.g.: Universal Software Radio Peripheral – Figure 3-1 (c);
- Different types of jammers/signal generators to produce intentional interference.
- Lab instruments devoted to the generation and analysis of RF signals, i.e.: signal and function generators, spectrum analyzers, oscilloscopes.

LINKS-ADS researchers have the necessary facilities to test GNSS devices in controlled environments (Figure 3-2) or in real outdoor scenarios (Figure 3-3).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3-1: NavX NCS GNSS signal generator (a), survey grade GNSS receivers (b) and USRP used as play back systems (c)

(a)

(b)

Figure 3-2: LINKS researchers working on lab spoofing tests (a) to assess vulnerabilities of high-end GNSS receivers employed in timing applications (b).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3-3: LINKS researchers working on outdoor tests to assess performance of GNSS receivers for precision agriculture (a) and new GNSS-IMU integrations for urban navigation (b); setup of a multi-antenna test bench used for spoofing detection (c).

3.13.3 1.1.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The main expected outcome is to put in place reconfigurable laboratory facilities for the testing of GNSS system, focusing particularly to GNSS interferences, e.g. jamming and spoofing. Such facilities will be strategic to boost the research activities of the group, including the investigation of AI/ML-based algorithms to the GNSS analysis (e.g. classification of GNSS threats), as well as to provide support to small companies for testing activities. Within this aim, a customized version of the research tool NGene2 (see previous section) for the scintillation monitoring has already been provided to the Navigation, Signal Analysis and Simulation (NavSAS) group and a support to its integration into the GNSS monitoring station is foreseen.

3.13.4 Foreseen research collaborations

LINKS-ADS will collaborate with the Navigation, Signal Analysis and Simulation (NavSAS) group, for research activities on GNSS-related topics, including the set-up of the GNSS monitoring station in the shared lab, hosted in LINKS premises. Collaborations with small companies, such as Italspazio s.r.l. and Origosat s.r.l., on GNSS interference testing activities, are also expected.

3.14 Space@UniTo

3.14.1 Group description

The group consists of researchers from the fields of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics. The background and the skills of the research group are therefore diverse, but they find common ground in the applications to topics relevant for industrial space applications. In the following, we describe the research activities by subject area.

- Flexible and lightweight photovoltaics based on perovskite and organic dyes for space applications
- Development of thermal and radiation shields
- Sorbents and Catalysis for CO₂ capture and production of synthetic fuels
- Development of X-ray sensors for imaging, spectroscopy and polarimetry for future X-ray missions
- The researchers working on the analytical study of systems in space have a background in nonlinear analysis, in particular theories of control and optimal control, study and classification of periodic orbits for singular systems, optimization problems, interactions with KAM theory and weak KAM, relativistic mechanics and astrophysics, study of the motion of bodies in a gravitational field in Newtonian and post-Newtonian physics. Researchers from the field of learning also participate in the project's research, with the aim of putting machine learning tools at the service of theoretical studies to explore natural or controlled trajectories that reach a given sequence of configurations.

Selected publications of the research groups relevant to Space4you:

- [1] Baldini L. et al. (2021). Design, construction, and test of the Gas Pixel Detectors for the IXPE mission. *ASTROPARTICLE PHYSICS*, vol. 133, p. 1-16, ISSN: 0927-6505, doi: 10.1016/j.astropartphys.2021.102628
- [2] Martin C. Weisskopf et al. (2021). The Imaging X-Ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE): Pre-Launch. *JOURNAL OF ASTRONOMICAL TELESCOPES, INSTRUMENTS, AND SYSTEMS*, p. 1-30, ISSN: 2329-4221, <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.8.2.026002>
- [3] Lorenzo Iorio, Matteo Luca Ruggiero (2022) Effect of Some Modified Models of Gravity on the Radial Velocity of Binary Systems, *Universe* (8)9, 443.
- [4] Matteo Luca Ruggiero, Angelo Tartaglia, Lorenzo Casalino (2022) Geometric definition of emission coordinates. *Adv.Space Res.* 69, 4221-4227.
- [5] Barutello V., Canneori G.M., Terracini S (2021) Symbolic Dynamics for the Anisotropic N-Centre Problem at Negative Energies, *Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis* volume 242, 1749–1834.
- [6] Barutello V., De Blasi I., Terracini S (2023) Chaotic dynamics in refraction galactic billiards, *Nonlinearity* volume 38 (8).

Selected projects of the research groups relevant to Space4you:

<i>STEPS, STEPS2</i>	<i>Past large regional projects coordinated by Thales Alenia Space. The group has contributed in the workpackages on thermal shields for Mars atmosphere entry and on composite materials for flexible inflatable structures/habitats.</i>
<i>PEROSKY</i>	<i>The project, founded by ASI, was focused on development and characterization of perovskite and other printable materials for energy application in space. Grant N° 2018-1-R.0</i>
<i>ROSSINI, ROSSINI-2, ROSSINI-3</i>	<i>The project, funded by ESA, has the purpose of evaluating the role of lithium hydride and LiBH₄ based materials and composites on space radiation shielding. ROSSINI-2 Grant N° EC-EES/2014.68/AM; ROSSINI-3 Grant N° 4000125785/18/NL/GLC</i>
<i>4AirCRAFT</i>	<i>The project, funded by the EU under the H2020 scheme, has the purpose of developing</i>

	<i>catalysts for the direct reduction of CO₂ to fuels.</i> <i>Grnt N° 101022633</i>
<i>ThermoProp III</i>	<i>The project, funded by ESA, has the purpose of measuring thermo-physical properties of metallic materials on ground and micro-gravity conditions on board of the ISS.</i> <i>Grant N° 420001436/01/NL/SH</i>
<i>X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF)</i>	<i>Project funded by Compagnia San Paolo; PI: Raffaella Bonino; budget = 172 000 €; period: 06/2021 - 12/2022</i>
<i>Detector Unit Data Analysis and exploitation</i>	<i>ASI-INFN agreement 2017-13-H.0 - Italian contribution to the NASA mission IXPE; funder: ASI; budget = 110 500 €; period: 2017 - 2019</i>
<i>New techniques for the detection of space debris</i>	<i>PI: Funded by Compagnia San Paolo; PI: Raffaella Bonino; budget = 75 000 €; period: 05/2017 - 12/2020</i>

3.14.2 Facilities

The Materials synthesis and characterization laboratories of the NIS Interdepartment Centre (www.nis.unito.it), hosted by the member Departments (Chemistry, Physics, Pharmacy, Earth Science, Biology) cover a very broad range of materials including structural and functional metals, polymers and composites, catalysts and sorbents, photo- and electro-chemical systems, bio-inorganic hybrid systems. The labs are equipped with state of the art instruments, which are shared not only internally, but also to external non academic users (Open Access Labs).

X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF): hosted in the Physics Department (UniTO) for the characterization of innovative X-ray sensors. The radiation source is an X-ray tube with a multi-anode to select the desired energy and two beam lines: one is unpolarized, the other one is polarized via Bragg diffraction on a polarizing crystal. Thanks to a handling system, the detector to be tested can measure both the unpolarized and polarized beam. By comparing these two signals X-ray sensors can be calibrated and characterized.

3.14.3 Outcomes from Space4You

The following outcomes are foreseen:

- Progress in the field of lightweight and flexible innovative solar cells for space applications by means of the development of novel organic and hybrid materials (e.g. electrodes, dyes and electrolytes) and cell chemistries.
- Exploitation of previous experiences on innovative thermal and radiation shields in the context of new projects
- New custom sensors will be tested and characterized for future X-ray missions.
- New results on the aggregation and movement of celestial bodies and other structures, optimization, stability and control of trajectories in space will be given. Combining deep learning methods and advanced mathematics, we aim to carry out systematic research for dynamic structures, their "complexity", and their connections. As possible applications of our research, in the context of space problems, we mention satellite orbits and the interception of dangerous objects (such as space debris). On this subject we intend to strengthen the research interactions between the mathematics department and the physics department and to expand the research group.

3.14.4 Foreseen research collaborations

Improvement of the involvement of UNITO in ASI and ESA projects by means of collaborations with other academic and industrial partners focused on

- modeling, synthesis, characterization and scale-up of innovative materials, composites and devices;
- machine learning and advanced mathematics applied for celestial body trajectory.

4 Staff

Name	Affiliation/Research Group	Brief cv
POLITECNICO DI TORINO		
Fabio Dovis	POLITO-DET/NavSAS	Fabio Dovis is a full professor at the Department of Electronics and Telecommunications of Politecnico di Torino, where he coordinates the Navigation Signal Analysis and Simulation – NavSAS - group, a joint research team of Politecnico di Torino and LINKS foundation. His technical expertise and research interests include the design of GPS and Galileo receivers, advanced signal processing for multipath mitigation, interference and spoofing countermeasures, as well as ionospheric monitoring. As of 2021 prof. Dovis supervised 19 Ph.D students on topics related to satellite navigation and positioning. He has a relevant experience in international collaborative projects as well as cooperation with industries and research centers. He authored more than 70 journal papers and more than 150 papers in proceedings of international conferences. He is member of the IEEE AESS navigation systems panel and he is currently serving in the Council of the US Institute of Navigation. He is a member of the GNSS Scientific Advisory Committee of the European Space Agency and he is also associated to the Italian Space Agency, as scientific support for matters related to the Galileo system.
Sabrina Corpino	POLITO-DIMEAS/STAR	Sabrina Corpino, PhD, is Associate Professor of Aerospace Systems at the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering of Politecnico di Torino. She is the Director of the Systems and Technologies for Aerospace Research Laboratory (STARlab) and she leads the CubeSat Programme of PoliTO. She has extensive experience in the field of space systems design and development, with focus on small space platforms and end-to-end missions. She coordinated three CubeSat flight missions developed by PoliTO launched in 2012, 2016 and 2023. She is involved in many research projects with major aerospace companies and public institutions. The research activity is documented through more than 80 articles published on scientific journals and presented at international conferences. She is member designated by ASI in the Board of Directors of e-Geos S.p.A., ASI/Telespazio Company.
Valentina Casalegno	POLITO-DISAT/GLANCE	Valentina Casalegno is Assistant Professor of Materials Science and Technology at DISAT-POLITO. Her research activity has been mostly dedicated to design, fabrication and characterization of joining materials and joints for advanced ceramic composites and ceramic/metal components. She is also working on surface modification (by thermal process, chemical etching, laser and plasma) and on developing, characterization and testing of materials for extreme applications and energy production, aerospace, automotive and nuclear plants. She is part of a team that aims at fostering high level research in Materials Science and Engineering through the participation to several projects and the cooperation with the most qualified international research centers and companies. She is member of The American Ceramic Society-Engineering Ceramic Division. 3 most relevant publications: [1] De Zanet, A., Casalegno, V., & Salvo, M. (2021). Laser surface texturing of ceramics and ceramic composite materials–A review. <i>Ceramics International</i> , 47(6), 7307-7320. [2]Casalegno, V., Valenza, F., Balagna, C., Sedlak, R., Girman, V., Salvo, M., & Ferraris, M. (2020). Characterisation of joined surface modified SiCf/SiC composites. <i>Ceramics International</i> , 46(4), 4159-4166. [3] Casalegno, V., Ferraris, M., Perero, S., Suess, M., Wilhelmi, C., Pedroni, M.,& Salvo, M. (2020). A plasma pre-treatment to improve

		adhesion on SiC and Si ₃ N ₄ ceramics. <i>Materials Letters</i> , 272, 127855.
Davide S. Paolino	POLITO-DIMEAS/MAM-MT	<p>Davide S. Paolino is a Full Professor at the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (DIMEAS) of the Politecnico di Torino.</p> <p>He is responsible for the following research activities in Politecnico di Torino – DIMEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanical characterization and modelling of composite materials; in particular, static, fatigue and crashworthiness response of structural laminates and bio-composites and non-destructive testing of composite plates and components. • Statistical analysis of experimental data. • Very-High-Cycle Fatigue (VHCF) of metallic materials. <p>He is author of more than 115 peer-reviewed papers published in international scientific journals or presented in international conferences, with more than 1800 citations yielding an h-Index of 24 (source: Scopus).</p> <p>3 most relevant publications:</p> <p>[1] Boursier Niuitta, C., Ciardiello, R., Tridello, A., & Paolino, D. S. (2023). Epoxy and Bio-Based Epoxy Carbon Fiber Twill Composites: Comparison of the Quasi-Static Properties. <i>Materials</i>, 16(4). https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16041601</p> <p>[2] Ciardiello, R., D'Angelo, D., Cagna, L., Croce, A., & Paolino, D. S. (2022). Effects of plasma treatments of polypropylene adhesive joints used in the automotive industry. <i>Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science</i>, 236(11), 6204–6218. https://doi.org/10.1177/09544062211065361</p> <p>[3] Boursier Niuitta, C., Tridello, A., Belingardi, G., & Paolino, D. S. (2021). Nondestructive determination of local material properties of laminated composites with the impulse excitation technique. <i>Composite Structures</i>, 262. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.113607</p>
Samuele Sampino	POLITO-DIMEAS/MAM-MT	<p>Samuele Sampino is a PhD student at the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (DIMEAS) of the Politecnico di Torino.</p> <p>He is at the first year of his PhD, aimed at the optimization of plasma treatments on composite fibres for the enhancement of the mechanical properties of structural composites.</p>
Elisa Fiume	POLITO- DISAT/LINCE	<p>Elisa Fiume is a dedicated researcher focused on the synthesis and processing of advanced ceramic materials for extreme environmental applications. With expertise in digital light processing and robocasting, Elisa contributed across different industrial/research fields, such as biomedicine, materials science and technology and aerospace. Additionally, Elisa possesses a complementary background in mathematical and physical modeling, along with expertise in computer-aided design (CAD). Her active engagement in national and international arenas is indicative of a proactive approach to fostering fruitful collaborations and her eagerness to transfer her expertise to space research reflects her adaptive approach to research.</p> <p>Publications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Schiavi et al. <i>Journal of the European Ceramic Society</i> 2022, 42, 6206-6212, DOI: 10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.06.022 [Q1, IF: 5.7]. 2. Fiume et al. <i>Ceramics International</i> 2022, 48, 35209-35216. DOI: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.08.121 [Q1; IF: 5.2]. 3. Fiume et al. <i>Acta Biomaterialia</i> 2021, 405-418. DOI: 10.1016/j.actbio.2020.10.027[Q1; IF: 9.7].
Bartolomeo Coppola	POLITO-DISAT/LINCE	<p>Bartolomeo's research activities are mainly dedicated to 3D printing of advanced ceramic materials, mainly through robocasting and digital light processing. Bartolomeo's strong ceramist background</p>

		<p>deals with several advanced ceramic materials such as aluminosilicates, alumina, zirconia and alumina-zirconia composites. All these materials are good candidates for numerous aerospace applications and Bartolomeo's research activities are mostly devoted to the optimization and engineering of the abovementioned materials through well-established and experimental synthesis and processing methods as well as by adding reinforcing agents, such as platelets, to improve thermal shock and fracture toughness properties.</p> <p>Publications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. B. Coppola et al., <i>Journal of the European Ceramic Society</i>, 2 (6) 2022, 2974-2982, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.01.024. [Q1, IF 5.7] 2. B. Coppola et al., <i>Ceramics International</i>, 47 (10) 2021, 13457-13468, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.01.204. [Q1, IF 5.2] 3. B. Inserra et al., <i>Journal of the European Ceramic Society</i>, 43 (7) 2023, 2907-2916, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.08.037. [Q1, IF 5.7]
Paolo Giaccone	POLITO-DET/TNG	<p>Paolo Giaccone is Full Professor in the Department of Electronics and Telecommunications of Politecnico di Torino. In 1998, he was technical consultant of the High-Speed Networks Research Department at Bell Laboratories (Lucent Technologies) in Holmdel (NJ, USA). In 2000-01 he was visiting researcher in the Electrical Engineering Department of Stanford University. In February 2002 he obtained the Ph.D. degree at Politecnico di Torino. Between February 2002 and October 2002, he held a PostDoc position at Politecnico di Torino and a PostDoc one at Stanford University between July 2002 and September 2002.</p> <p>His main research interests regard computer network modeling and performance evaluation, event-driven simulations, network control, data plane programmability, satellite networks.</p> <p>Recent publications:</p> <p>[1] Cohen, Itamar; Chiasserini, Carla Fabiana; Giaccone, Paolo; Scalosub, Gabriel, <i>Dynamic Service Provisioning in the Edge-cloud Continuum with Bounded Resources</i>, in: IEEE-ACM TRANSACTIONS ON NETWORKING, 2023</p> <p>[2] Adeppady, Madhura; Giaccone, Paolo; Karl, Holger; Chiasserini, Carla Fabiana, <i>Reducing Microservices Interference and Deployment Time in Resource-constrained Cloud Systems</i>, in: IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON NETWORK AND SERVICE MANAGEMENT, 2023</p> <p>[3] Lotfimahyari, Iman; Sviridov, German; Giaccone, Paolo; Bianco, Andrea, <i>Data plane assisted state replication with Network Function Virtualization</i>, in: IEEE SYSTEMS JOURNAL, 2022</p>
Giuseppe Scellato	POLITO-DIGEP	<p>Giuseppe Scellato holds a Ph.D. in Economics and is Full Professor at Politecnico di Torino, where he teaches corporate finance and economics and management of innovation. From 2015 to 2018 he has been the Vice Dean of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Management. Since 2018 he is the president and CEO of the Innovative Companies Incubator (I3P) of Politecnico di Torino. Since 2017 he is a member of the board of the Future Urban Legacy Lab (FULL) at Politecnico di Torino. Since 2008 he is research affiliate of the Bureau of Research in Innovation Complexity and Knowledge (BRICK) at Collegio Carlo Alberto.</p> <p>His main research interests are in the areas of economics and management of innovation, industry dynamics, the economic analysis of intellectual property rights, and the economics of science.</p>

		<p>His scientific publications have appeared in leading international journals, including Science, Nature, Journal of Management Studies, Journal of Corporate Finance, Research Policy, Journal of Banking and Finance, Journal of Business Research, and Cambridge Journal of Economics. He has been guest editor for different journals in the field of innovation studies.</p> <p>In recent years, he has been the principal investigator of research projects funded by the European Commission, the European Patent Office, the Joint Research Center, the European Investment Bank, the National Bureau of Economic Research. He has been member of expert groups and committees for the evaluation of public policies for research and innovation in different Italian regions. He has managed numerous consulting project with public and private organisations in the areas of intellectual property and innovation.</p>
Paolo Maggiore	POLITO-DIMEAS/ASTRA	<p>Paolo Maggiore is a full professor at the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering of Politecnico di Torino, where he coordinates the ASTRA group (Additive manufacturing for Systems and sTRuctures in Aerospace). His technical expertise and research interests include the design of aerospace systems integrating sensors to implement diagnostic, prognostic, control and monitoring functions. Paolo Maggiore is the reference person for the optical sensor applications in the Mechanical and Aerospace environment in the Photonext interdepartmental center. As of 2022 prof. Maggiore supervised more than 20 PhD students on topics related to aerospace systems. He has a relevant experience in international collaborative projects as well as cooperation with industries and research centers. He authored more than 100 journal papers and more than 200 papers in proceedings of international conferences.</p>
Giuliana Mattiazzo	POLITO-DIMEAS	
Giuseppe C. Marano	POLITO-DISEG	<p>Structural engineers recognized for his research and expertise in the field of structural optimization in new or existing buildings or bridges and in the identification and characterization of bridges and structures and seismic protection. His international experience is quite large, as he has been Visiting assistant professor at Cambridge (2002), associate professor in 2011 at Politecnico di Bari, visiting Professor in Loughborough University (2012), and at Hunan University (China) in 2014. He has been research fellow at the SIBERC (Sustainable and Innovative Bridge Engineering Research Center) at the Fuzhou University (China) since 2014; in the same university he had been full Professor in Structural Design from 2015 to 2018. From 2018 is full professor in structural Design at Politecnico di Torino. He is also member and founder of the interdepartmental centre for Artificial Intelligence (AI@polito), and director of ARTISTE (ARTificial Intelligence in STRuctural Engineering).</p> <p>He participated in several European project-funded projects as a COST Action TU1406 “European standardization of quality specifications for roadway bridge” (Italian delegate) or the Rice Project ADDOPTML (Italian PI) to support a network to create and test an holistic machine learning aided optimum design-manufacturing process of civil structures by developing strong synergies among a multi-disciplinary team of academic experts and SME. He also organised some recent events dealing with structural optimization in civil engineering as co-chair of OPTARC2019 – 1st International Conference on Optimization Driven Architectural Design and the Eurasian Opensees Days (EOS2022)</p>
Stefano Scialò	POLITO-DISMA	<p>Stefano Scialò is Associate Professor at Dipartimento di Scienze Matematiche “G.L. Lagrange” of Politecnico di Torino. He received his Master Degree in Aerospace Engineering in 2007, and the PhD degree in Mathematics for Engineering in 2014, both from Politecnico di Torino. Following his PhD studies, he was first a postdoctoral fellow and then Assistant professor at the DISMA. His research interests include flow simulations in complex geometries, development and analysis of discretization strategies on non-conforming meshes and polygonal/polyhedral numerical methods,</p>

		<p>uncertainty quantification techniques, PDE-constrained optimization, high-performance computing techniques. He authored more 38 papers on subjects related to Numerical Analysis with 996 citations (H-index 18) (source: Scopus – July 2023).</p>
Piero Boccardo	POLITO-DIST	<p>Full Professor of Geomatics at the DIST, Polytechnic of Turin, teaches remote sensing at the master's degree programs in Environmental and Land Engineering, Geography and Urban and Regional Planning.</p> <p>Since 2006, Director of ITHACA (Information Technology for Humanitarian Assistance, Cooperation and Action), a research association founded by Turin Polytechnic and Compagnia di San Paolo, and from 2021 President of Ithaca Srl, active in the emergency management and security sector. From 2012 to 2018, President of the public company (Piedmont Region, City of Turin, Metropolitan City and GTT) 5T, operating in the sector of mobility, ITS (Intelligent Transportation Systems) and infomobility. Research fellow in Earth Observation at Links foundation participated by Politecnico di Torino and Compagnia di San Paolo. Is now President of Urban Lab a joint association between the City Of Torino and Compagnia di San Paolo</p> <p>Graduated from the Polytechnic of Turin, PhD in "Geodetic and Topographical Sciences", from 2011 to 2019 he was the President of the Italian Association of Remote Sensing (AIT); member since 1997 of the Scientific and Executive Councils of the ASITA Federation (Italian Federation of Scientific Associations for Territorial and Environmental Information); from 2008 to 2012 chairman of the Working Group 1 (Remote Sensing and Disasters) of Commission VIII (Remote Sensing Application) of ISPRS (International Society of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing. From 2021 Politecnico di Torino delegate for Earth Observation programmes</p> <p>Author of more than 250 National and International scientific publications, he has participated as lecturer and chairman in more than 100 national and international scientific conferences.</p>
Luca Sterpone	POLITO-DAUIN/CAD	<p>Luca Sterpone is Full Professor and Vice-Director at the Department of Control and Computer Engineering (DAUIN) at Polytechnic of Turin.</p> <p>Luca Sterpone received the MS degree in Computer Engineering (2003) and the PhD degree in Computer and System Engineering (2007) from Politecnico di Torino, Italy. He has been technology transfer engineer at Boeing Satellite Systems, El Segundo, CA (USA) in 2006 and 2007 and technology transfer engineer at EADS, Suresnes - Paris (France) in 2008.</p> <p>The research activity of Luca Sterpone focuses on computer engineering, and it covers several multidisciplinary topics such as reconfigurable computing, computer-aided design algorithms, fault tolerance and reliability. Luca is the author of more than 200 papers and he received several awards for his research activity such as the Best Paper award at the IEEE European Test Symposium (2005) and the EDAA Outstanding Dissertation Award in 2007. He has been Program Co-chair of HiPEAC Reconfigurable Computing Workshop (2012) and General Chair of HiPEAC WRC (2013). He serves as member within the Program Committee of several events such as RADECS, NSREC, ISIE. He has an active collaboration with several companies: Xilinx, Actel, European Space Agency (ESA), Boeing Satellite Systems, Thales Alenia Space, EADS.</p> <p>Luca Sterpone has been appointed as component of evaluator experts, Gruppo Esperti Valutatori for the Area 9 (GEV-09) on industrial and information engineering by the Italian Agency for the evaluation of the Universities and Research (ANVUR -Agenzia Nazionale di Valutazione del Sistema Universitario e della Ricerca) for the evaluation of the research quality in VQR 2015-2019. Luca Sterpone is an evaluator expert for the European Commission (EC) for the Horizon 2020 Programme, specifically on the following review tasks: 2014: H2020 FET HPC, 2017: H2020 ICT, 2017/2019:</p>

		EXANEST project Monitoring, 2020: EURO-HPC. Luca Sterpone is a member of the College of Expert Reviewers of the European Science Foundation (ESF) in the Period 2019-2022.
Lia Morra	POLITO-DAUIN/CAD	<p>Lia Morra is Assistant Professor with Tenure Track (RTDb) at Politecnico di Torino in the GRAINS (GRAphics and INtelligent Systems). Previously, she with the Research & Development team of the Italian company im3D, where she developed pattern recognition and processing algorithms for medical image interpretation. From 2015 to 2018, she served as Chief Scientific Officer for im3D, leading a multidisciplinary team working on the application of Artificial Intelligence / Computer Aided Diagnosis and digital imaging solutions to cancer screening and prevention, with a diverse research program at the intersection of machine learning, human-computer interaction for radiology and statistics / epidemiology.</p> <p>Her current research interests are mostly focused on deep learning, machine learning and neuro-symbolic techniques for semantic visual interpretation, image analysis and related applications. She is author of one book and more than 50 technical papers in international journals, conference proceedings and edited collections. She is an IEEE Senior Member and a member of the AAPM (American Association of Physicists in Medicine) Computer Aided Detection in Diagnostic Imaging (CAD) Subcommittee.</p>
Rosario Milazzo	POLITO-DAUIN	<p>Rosario Milazzo obtained the bachelor's degree in Computer Engineering from Politecnico di Torino in 2020 and master's degree in 2022.</p> <p>In 2022, after his master's degree, he started working at Politecnico di Torino as scholarship holder in the GRAINS research group at the Department of Control and Computer Engineering (DAUIN) of the Politecnico di Torino. In February 2023, he was selected as PhD candidate in Computer Engineering funded by NODES.</p> <p>The main topic of his research is the optimization and fault tolerance of neural networks in the field of mobility and satellites.</p>
Riccardo Apa	POLITO-DIMEAS	<p>Riccardo Apa received his bachelor's degree in Aerospace Engineering from Politecnico di Torino in 2018. After attending the first year of the Space Engineering master in the same institute, he won the "Double Degree" competition which led him to obtain, in addition to the master degree from Politecnico di Torino, the title "Diplome d'ingenieur" at ISAE-Supaero in 2021. In 2021, he was selected for an 18 months project as Intern at NASA /JPL where he did research on Modeling and Control of Space Distributed Systems.</p> <p>In 2022 he started working at Politecnico di Torino as a researcher. In November of the same year he was selected as PhD candidate in Aerospace Engineer.</p> <p>His research interests include Dynamics and Control of Distributed Space systems, Space Trajectory Optimization and Space Debris Monitoring. He's actually working on Optimal Trajectories applied to Space Logistics problems both in interorbital and in interplanetary environment.</p> <p>Publications :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Apa, R., Quadrelli, M. B., & Beauchamp, R. M. (2022, March). <i>Dynamics and Control of Helical Arrays in Low Earth Orbit</i>. In <i>2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference (AERO)</i> (pp. 1-20). IEEE. 2. Apa, R., Bonaccorsi, S., Armellin, R., & Pirovano, L. (2018, April). <i>Combined Optical and Radar Measurements for Orbit Determination</i>. In <i>2018 ESA Space Debris Conference</i> 3. Apa, R., Mao, P., Quadrelli, M. B., & Beauchamp, R. M. (2022, June). <i>Effective Sensitivity Analyses of Radar</i>

		<i>Systems in Formation Flying using Differential Algebra. In 11th "International Workshop on Satellite Constellations & Formation Flying" (IWSCFF 2022).</i>
Elettra D'Amico	POLITO-DIGEP	<p>Elettra D'Amico is a dedicated researcher at the Department of Management and Production Engineering of the Polytechnic University of Turin. She holds a master's degree in Management Engineering, specializing in Entrepreneurship and Innovation, and a Ph.D. in Management Engineering from the Polytechnic University of Turin.</p> <p>Her research interest mainly focuses on the impacts of emerging technologies on entrepreneurship, innovation, and regional entrepreneurship.</p> <p>[1] FILIERI, R., D'AMICO, E., DESTEFANIS, A., PAOLUCCI, E. AND RAGUSEO, E., (2021) "Artificial intelligence (AI) for tourism: an European-based study on successful AI tourism start-ups," <i>International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management</i>, 33(11), pp. 4099–4125.</p> <p>[2] COLOMBARI, R., D'AMICO, E., AND PAOLUCCI, E., (2021) "Can challenge-based learning be effective online? A case study using experiential learning theory," <i>CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation</i>, 5(1), pp. 40–48.</p> <p>[3] COLOMBELLI, A., D'AMICO, E., PAOLUCCI, E., RICCI, R., (2018), "Attività e modelli universitari di trasferimento tecnologico", <i>Economia e Società Regionale</i>, 3, 10-27, Franco Angeli, 10.3280/ES2018-003002</p>
UNIVERSITY OF TURIN		
Raffaella Bonino	UniTO (Dept of Physics)	<p>Raffaella Bonino is Associate Professor at the Department of Physics of University of Torino. She works in the field of experimental astroparticle physics. She is / has been member of some of the major international collaborations, i.e., for the experiment Pierre Auger Observatory and the NASA space missions Fermi and IXPE.</p> <p>She is professor for the Bachelor and Master Degree Courses of Physics and for the 2nd level Master in <i>Mathematical and Physical Methods for Space Sciences</i>.</p> <p>Publications:</p> <p>[1] Baldini L. et al. (2021). Design, construction, and test of the Gas Pixel Detectors for the IXPE mission. <i>ASTROPARTICLE PHYSICS</i>, vol. 133, p. 1-16, ISSN: 0927-6505, doi: 10.1016/j.astropartphys.2021.102628</p> <p>[2] Martin C. Weisskopf et al. (2021). The Imaging X-Ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE): Pre-Launch. <i>JOURNAL OF ASTRONOMICAL TELESCOPES, INSTRUMENTS, AND SYSTEMS</i>, p. 1-30, ISSN: 2329-4221, https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.8.2.026002</p> <p>[3] N. Cibrario, M. Negro, N. Moriakov, R. Bonino et al., "Joint machine learning and analytic track reconstruction for X-ray polarimetry with gas pixel detectors", <i>A&A</i> 674, A107 (2023), https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202346302</p>
Roberta Sirovich	UniTO (Dept. of Mathematics)	<p>Roberta Sirovich is assistant professor (researcher) at the Department of Mathematics "G. Peano" of the University of Torino. Her research interests range in (1) the area stochastic models, from their definition and deduction of theoretical properties to the statistical estimation of the parameters and (2) in the area of statistical learning and development of advanced learning methods for complex data. Her experience is multidisciplinary with a strong interest in Biostatistics and Bioinformatics. She is professor for the Bachelor and Master Degree Courses of Computer Science and Biology and for the 2nd level Master in <i>Mathematical and Physical Methods for Space Sciences</i>.</p> <p>Recent Publications:</p>

		<p>1. CONNECTOR, fitting and clustering of longitudinal data to reveal a new risk stratification system (with S. Pernice et al.). <i>Bioinformatics</i>, Volume 39, Issue 5, 2023.</p> <p>2. Dissecting MRD Kinetics By Automated Computational Analysis to Improve Outcome Prediction in Mantle Cell Lymphoma: A Bioinformatic Substudy from the Fondazione Italiana Linfomi (FIL) MCL0208 Clinical Trial (with F. Cordero, S. Ferrero et al.). <i>Blood</i>, 140 (Supplement 1): 9375–9377, 2022.</p> <p>3. Multi-institutional analysis of outcomes for thermosphere microwave ablation treatment of colorectal liver metastases: the SMAC study (with F. De Cobelli, M. Calandri, A. Della Corte et al.). <i>Eur Radiol.</i>, 32 (6), 4147-4159, 2022.</p>
Gabriele Ricchiardi	UniTO (Dept. of Chemistry)	<p>Associate Professor of Physical Chemistry at the Department of Chemistry, University of Torino. His research focuses on porous materials as adsorbents, catalysts and functional materials. In the field of space applications, he has worked on thermal shields and materials for inflatable structures. He is Director of the NIS Interdepartment Centre on Materials Science (www.nis.unito.it), coordinates the Space&Aviation Interest Group at UniTO (connecting all UniTO researcher interested in Space and Aviation applications) and represents the University in the Distretto Aerospaziale Piemonte (DAP).</p> <p><i>Recent Publications:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) V Finelli, V Gentilin, G Mossotti, G Ricchiardi, A Piovano, V Crocellà, The role of porosity and acidity in the catalytic upcycling of polyethylene, <i>Catalysis Today</i> 419, 114142 (2023) 2) M Giuliano, MC Valsania, P Ticali, E Sartoretti, S Morandi, S Bensaid, G. Ricchiardi, M. Sgroi, Characterization of the evolution of noble metal particles in a commercial three-way catalyst: Correlation between real and simulated ageing <i>Catalysts</i> 11 (2), 247 (2019) 3) M Signorile, JG Vitillo, M D'Amore, V Crocellà, G Ricchiardi, S Bordiga Characterization and Modeling of Reversible CO₂ Capture from Wet Streams by a MgO/Zeolite Y Nanocomposite <i>The Journal of Physical Chemistry C</i> 123 (28), 17214-17224 (2019)
Diego Berti	UniTO (Dept. of Mathematics)	<p>D. Berti is a Research Fellow (rtd-a) at the Department of Mathematics “G. Peano” of the University of Turin, where he joined the group of Nonlinear Differential Equations. His research has focused on various theoretical aspects of solutions of Partial Differential Equations. His contributions and expertise include geometric properties of solutions of nonlinear PDEs, existence, uniqueness and regularity of traveling-wave solutions to diffusion-convection reaction equations, regularity properties of so-called Tropical Climate Models, global well-posedness problems related to Complex Bodies. Three main recent publications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) D. Berti, L. Bisconti, P.M. Mariano. Dynamics of complex bodies with memory and vector-valued microstructure: existence and uniqueness, <i>Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena</i>, vol. 446, April 2023, Art. 133683, 2023. 2) D. Berti, L. Bisconti, D. Catania. A regularity criterion for a 3D tropical climate model with damping, <i>Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications</i>, 2023, 518(1), 16685. 3) D. Berti, A. Corli, L. Malaguti. Diffusion-convection reaction equations with sign-changing diffusivity and bistable reaction term, <i>Nonlinear Analysis: Real World Applications</i>, 2022, 103579.

Simone Galliano	UniTO (Dept. of Chemistry)	<p>Research Fellow (RTD-A) at the Department of Chemistry, University of Torino. He received his Master Degree in Industrial Chemistry in 2012, and the PhD degree in Chemical and Material Sciences in 2017, both from University of Torino. He is author of 23 peer-reviewed papers published on international scientific journals, with more than 900 citations yielding an h-Index of 14 (source: Scopus). His research focuses on the development of organic and hybrid photovoltaics, from materials to complete devices. His expertise is mainly related to the synthesis of organic dyes, the formulation of electrolytes, and their physicochemical and electrochemical characterization.</p> <p>3 most relevant publications:</p> <p>[1] Zanetti G., Carlotto A., Lam Tran T., Szczurek A., Babiarczuk B., Sayginer O., Varas S., Krzak J., Bursi O., Zonta D., Baldi G., Bonomo M., Galliano S., Barolo C., Bazzanella N., Pietralunga S., Chiasera A. (2023) Under bending optical assessment of flexible glass based multilayer structures fabricated on polymeric substrates. <i>Optical Materials: X</i>, 19, 100241.</p> <p>[2] Mariotti N., Viada G., Galliano S., Menozzi A., Tammaro F., Gianelli W., Bonomo M., Barolo C. (2023) Increasing circular and bio-based content of a thermosetting polyurethane for encapsulation of optoelectronic devices: A multivariate investigation. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>, 408, 137161</p> <p>[3] Galliano S., Bella F., Bonomo M., Viscardi G., Gerbaldi C., Boschloo G., Barolo, C. (2020) Hydrogel electrolytes based on xanthan gum: Green route towards stable dye-sensitized solar cells. <i>Nanomaterials</i>, 10(8), 1585.</p>
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Micaela Troglia Gamba	LINKS-ADS	<p>Micaela Troglia Gamba received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in Electronics Engineering from Politecnico di Torino, Italy, in 2007 and 2011, respectively. She is currently a Senior Researcher within the Artificial Intelligence, Data and Space (ADS) area of LINKS Foundation, Torino, Italy, working as a hardware–software designer and developer of new digital architectures for global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receivers.</p> <p>Her main research interests include the implementation of interference detection and mitigation algorithms and GNSS authentication techniques on real-time GNSS software receivers, running on general-purpose processors, and low-cost ARM-based embedded platforms.</p> <p>Please refer to this link for the list of all publications, of which the three most relevant are listed below:</p> <p>[1] Troglia Gamba, M.; Nicola, M.; Motella, B. Computational Load Analysis of a Galileo OSNMA-Ready Receiver for ARM-Based Embedded Platforms. <i>Sensors</i> 2021, 21, 467. https://doi.org/10.3390/s21020467</p> <p>[2] E. Falletti, M. T. Gamba and M. Pini, "Design and Analysis of Activation Strategies for Adaptive Notch Filters to Suppress GNSS Jamming," in <i>IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems</i>, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 3718-3734, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAES.2020.2982301</p> <p>[3] Nicola, Mario, Motella, Beatrice, Gamba, Micaela Troglia, "GPS Chimera: A Software Receiver Implementation," <i>Proceedings of the 34th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation (ION GNSS+ 2021)</i>, St. Louis, Missouri, September 2021, pp. 4264-4273. https://doi.org/10.33012/2021.18127</p>
Olivier Terzo		<p>Olivier Terzo holds Ph.D. in Electronic Engineering and Communications and M.Sc. Degree in Computer Engineering from both achieved at Politecnico di Torino. He is currently the Head of the CPE Advanced Computing, Photonics and Electromagnetics</p>

		<p>Research Domain with a staff of 25 Researchers at the LINKS Foundation Applied Research Center. He was the Technical and Scientific coordinator of the OPERA H2020 project, and he was the co-design and dissemination manager of the LEXIS project. Currently, he is the coordinator of the ACROSS EuroHPC project, a delegate member at ETP4HPC and an active member of the HIPEAC community. He peer-reviewed several journals.</p>
Paolo Viviani		<p>Paolo Viviani earned a degree in theoretical physics and a PhD in computer science both at University of Torino. He is now Senior Researcher at LINKS Foundation.</p> <p>His main research areas are High-Performance Computing, Quantum Computing and systems for Machine Learning/AI.</p> <p>His current activity focuses on HPC and scientific computing topics like the acceleration of complex scientific and industrial workflows on large scale HPC infrastructures and optimization algorithms for near-term analog quantum hardware.</p> <p>Among his several publications, it is worth citing:</p> <p>[1] Savio, P; Scionti, A; Vitali, G; Viviani, P; Vercellino, C; Terzo, O; Nguyen, Hn; Magarielli, D; Spano, E; Marconcini, M; Poli, F. Accelerating legacy applications with spatial computing devices / - In: THE JOURNAL OF SUPERCOMPUTING. - ISSN 0920-8542. (2022). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-022-04925-2]</p> <p>[2] Vercellino, C; Scionti, A; Varavallo, G; Viviani, P; Vitali, G; Terzo, O. A machine learning approach for an HPC use case: The jobs queuing time prediction / - In: FUTURE GENERATION COMPUTER SYSTEMS. - ISSN 0167-739X. - 143:(2023), pp. 215-230. [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2023.01.020]</p> <p>[3] Scionti A., Viviani, P., Vitali, G., Vercellino, C., & Terzo, O. (2022). Enabling the HPC and Artificial Intelligence Cross-Stack Convergence at the Exascale Level. In <i>HPC, Big Data, and AI Convergence Towards Exascale</i> (pp. 37–58). https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003176664-3</p>
Giuseppe Caragnano	LINKS-CPE	<p>Giuseppe Caragnano is senior researcher and program manager at Advance Computing, Photonics and Electromagnetics and Application Research Domain (CPE) of LINKS Foundation. He obtained a Degree in Telecommunications Engineering from the Polytechnic of Turin in 2006. He works in many European projects supporting co-design for big data and HPC convergence solutions. Supporting SMEs on technology/platform choices for the acceleration of applications on infrastructures oriented to High Performance Computing, Computing Continuum and reverse engineering for adaptation and integration on cloud oriented infrastructures.</p>
Federico Stirano	LINKS-CPE	<p>Federico Stirano, is a Senior Researcher at LINKS Foundation. He got a Degree in Telecommunication Engineering in 2002 from the Polytechnic of Turin. Over the years he worked on several research topics, including low-power embedded platform, IoT and energy related issues. Currently, he is working in the CPE research domain, dealing with the development of applications to exploit the potentialities of Computing Continuum, integrating aspects of cloud and edge computing.</p>
Fabrizio Bertone	LINKS-CPE	<p>Fabrizio Bertone is working as a researcher in the Advanced Computing department of LINKS Foundation. He has been involved in several European and national projects, in fields ranging from energy and healthcare to agriculture and manufacture, using technologies like Cloud Computing, IoT and Distributed Ledgers. He is currently working on the implementation of an edge computing</p>

		system for the detection of production defects in the beverage bottling and packaging industry. He holds a master's degree in Computer Engineering from the Polytechnic University of Turin (Italy).
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5 Knowledge portal

A first relevant outcome of the project is the creation of a Space4You knowledge portal, i.e. an accessible **database of the competences and skills available in the research aerospace ecosystem**.

The competences of the different partners are very diverse and wide in scope, but they cover all the classical phases of the design and development of a space system, targeting the mission aspects, the upstream deployment as well as the downstream application in the fields of Communications, Earth Observation, Navigation and Space Exploration. For this reason, the first phase of the setting of the Lab will target a coordination and systematic survey of the different competences, coordinating them and fostering collaborations and synergies, in order to offer to the industrial world a unique, reliable interface for their needs.

The Space4 for Knowledge portal will be coordinated with the **Knowledge Share platform (KS)** of NODES – see **Innovation Booster** – to match companies needs and research offering and generate interactions for university technology transfer, academic research results and industrial innovation and development.

Each research activity performed in Space4You will provide together with the scientific results, a contribution to the portal, in order to disseminate the information, while putting it in the global framework of a fairly complete technical and research support to companies that will approach the lab.

The competence database will be accessible through a public web interface and will report the different competence topics and reference contact persons. It will be deployed starting from the competences of the partners of the flagship project, but it is intended as a living database, that will be enriched along the project and maintained, as a reference point for a global picture of the technical competences of the Aerospace research in the area. This will be a fundamental tool also for the **Competence Booster**, that will leverage on it to foster the growth of the advanced skills in the Aerospace sector filling the gap between research and industry.